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Executive Summary

This document is prepared in the context of the COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE) project. This report presents the outcomes and insights derived from the first phase of the piloting activities. The primary aim of this piloting phase is to test the ERA Hubs framework in the Czech ecosystem with the involvement of the Danish and Dutch ecosystems for the validation of inter-regional and trans-regional cooperation. To this end, this report presents the use cases analysed in the Czech, Danish and Dutch ecosystems and puts forth the insights related to the testing of the ERA Hubs framework and its associated tools.

The information gathered in this report serves to sustain the development of the ERA Hubs framework on several dimensions. First, testing the model in different ecosystems across Europe and with a different thematic focus helps the COOPERATE project team to improve and refine the framework and the associated tools, most notably the Playbook, the Toolbox and the maturity self-assessment tool. In addition, the piloting of the activities in Czechia, together with the additional four use cases from the Netherlands and Denmark sheds light on the applicability of the framework from different perspectives:

- The Czech pilot use case illustrates the **needs of an emerging ecosystem** and how the ERA Hubs framework and tools can contribute to its future development (i.e. AI in the Prague region),
- The Dutch case study analyses the needs and challenges related to **ecosystem stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration settings**,
- The Dutch use cases on the **semiconductor and health ecosystems** shed light on the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework in the light of the needs and characteristics of these ecosystems.
- The Danish use cases on **life sciences and sustainable technologies** contribute to a better understanding of the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework and provides a good basis to improve the tools to measure the maturity of ecosystems (Key Performance Indicators, KPIs).

These use cases and case studies shed light on the needs of ecosystems and point at challenges that are common to all of them – most notably those related to talent, access to innovation support and funding, governance mechanisms to foster collaboration, interregional collaboration, the development of joint strategies across quadruple helix stakeholder, as well as the challenges to involve civil society in R&I collaborative activities.

Some aspects included in this document were presented and discussed at the COOPERATE Co-creation session that took place on the 23rd of September 2024, together with the concrete Key Performance Indicators developed to measure the maturity of R&I ecosystems. The combination of use cases and concrete indicators to measure maturity led to important suggestions from participants to improve the measurement tools. These suggestions will be considered in the further refinement of the KPIs for the self-assessment tool.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

Acronym	Stands for
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ČVUT/CTU	Czech Technical University
D	Deliverable
Dx.x	Deliverable Number
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LERL	Local Ecosystem Readiness Level
NLP	Natural Language Processing
R&I	Research and Innovation
RIS	European (Regional) Innovation Scoreboard
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TU/e	Eindhoven University of Technology
WP	Work Package

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Introduction

This document is prepared in the context of the COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE) project. This report presents the outcomes and insights derived from the first phase of the piloting activities. The primary aim of this piloting phase is to test the ERA Hubs framework in the Czech ecosystem with the involvement of the Danish and Dutch ecosystems for the validation of inter-regional and trans-regional cooperation. To this end, this report presents the use cases analysed in the Czech, Danish and Dutch ecosystems and puts forth the insights related to the testing of the ERA Hubs framework and its associated tools.

To this end, this report presents the use cases analysed in the Czech, Danish and Dutch ecosystems and puts forth the insights related to the testing of the ERA Hubs framework and associated tools in each of them.

This report is structured as follows:

- The first chapter provides information about the project, the purpose of the piloting activities and the methodology.
- The second chapter focuses on the **piloting activities carried out in Czechia**, most notably in the Artificial Intelligence ecosystem in Prague. This chapter provides information about the piloting activities, the insights gained through them as well as on the conclusions and lessons learnt for the next steps of the development of the ERA Hubs framework, its related tools and the possible policy recommendations. This Czech pilot use case contributes to a better understanding of the needs of an emerging ecosystem and how the ERA Hubs framework and tools can contribute to its future development (i.e. AI in the Prague region),
- The third chapter focuses on the interregional collaboration dimension of ERA Hubs. It does so by analysing the thematic specialisation, collaboration patterns and stakeholder engagement at national, regional and ecosystem level. The case study on stakeholder engagement is particularly interesting in this regard as it provides useful insights from the Brainport-Lyngby collaboration setting.
- The fourth chapter presents the use cases that have been developed in the Netherlands and in Denmark. The Dutch use cases on the semiconductor and health ecosystems shed light on the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework in the light of the needs and characteristics of these ecosystems; while the Danish use cases on life sciences and sustainable technologies contribute to a better understanding of the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework and provides a good basis to improve the tools to measure the maturity of ecosystems (KPIs).

1. Context and framework

COOPERATE is a Horizon Europe project that aims to develop and pilot the ERA Hub concept, hence implementing the first steps of the ERA Policy Action 15 “Building up research and innovation ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness”¹. Drawing on the successful experiences of the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their R&I ecosystems, the aim of the COOPERATE project is to create a methodology to support the creation and development of ERA Hubs and to set the basis for the creation of a pan-European network of ERA Hubs.

The COOPERATE project constitutes an opportunity to co-design the European Research Area (ERA) Hub concept within various regional and thematic focal areas. As home countries of the partners of the COOPERATE project, Czechia, together with Denmark and the Netherlands have been chosen as use cases illustrating the application of the ERA Hubs framework, its challenges and possibilities. These use cases serve to test, validate and finetune the main dimensions (lines of action) of an ERA Hub, the core elements of the interaction within an ecosystem, as well as the interregional collaboration dynamics between ecosystems. Figure 1 presents the framework used for the piloting of the ERA Hubs framework and tools in the COOPERATE project. It consists of three main phases: it starts with a ‘discovery’ phase that allows to identify the main actors and dimensions of a given ecosystem through mapping exercises. In the second phase, the feedback from the actors regarding their needs and challenges for collaboration are gathered and analysed. The third phase focuses on testing the tools and identifying topics and needs for future policy recommendations.

Figure 1: Framework for Piloting ERA Hubs

Source: COOPERATE project.

The regions selected to test the ERA Hubs framework – Prague (Czechia), Brainport region (the Netherlands), and Copenhagen (Denmark) are innovation leaders according to the European Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS)². This tool provides an assessment of the relative research and innovation performance at regional level. The selected regions present, however, varying degrees of development and performance when looking at specific ecosystems (i.e. thematic-based ecosystems), each of them facing specific challenges and contexts. The use cases developed by the COOPERATE project therefore serve to test the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework and tools in a diversity of contexts.

¹ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

² <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

2. Piloting the ERA Hubs framework: the Czech use case

The ERA Hubs pilot in the Czech Republic was based on the analysis of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) ecosystem in the Prague region. The selection of this ecosystem lies on several reasons. First, from a thematical perspective, the choice of AI derives from the alignment with the National Strategy for artificial intelligence in the Czech Republic whose aim is *“to position the country as a leader in AI innovation and application. The strategy focuses on fostering a robust AI ecosystem by supporting research and development, enhancing education and skills, and encouraging collaboration between academia, industry, and government. Key objectives include creating a favorable regulatory environment, investing in AI infrastructure, and promoting ethical AI practices”*³. From a geographical point of view, the selection of Prague is based on the fact that the Czech Technical University in Prague is one of the partners in the consortium and the fact that the Czech RIS3 strategy mapping indicated that the vast majority of innovation ecosystems are located very close to the three largest cities in the Czech Republic - Prague, Brno and Ostrava (see Figure 2)⁴.

The application of the ERA Hubs framework in Czechia is aligned with the Czech National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation 2021-2027. This alignment is visible topic wise, as the strategy indicates that digital technologies (including AI) constitute strategic priorities. The ERA Hubs framework is also aligned in terms of the process to achieve the goals, since the strategy encourages the *“collaboration between public and private sectors, academia, and international partners to drive technological advancements and economic growth”*. Furthermore, the strategy also emphasizes the importance of regional development, ensuring that innovation benefits are distributed across the country⁵.

The piloting followed several phases, which included an initial mapping of activities, actors and challenges; two surveys to stakeholders and companies; a roundtable; and a workshop. The insights gathered in these activities are presented in the next pages before concluding with the main lessons learnt during the process.

3 Source: National Artificial Intelligence Strategy of the Czech Republic. Online. 2019. Dostupné z: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.mpo.gov.cz/assets/en/guidepost/for-the-media/press-releases/2019/5/NAIS_eng_web.pdf. [cit. 2024-09-11]

4 Source: Přehled inovační infrastruktury. Online. In: RIS3.cz. Př. n. l. Dostupné z: <https://www.ris3.cz/monitoring/regionalni-dimenze-ris3/inovacni-ekosystemy-v-krajich/mapovani-inovacnich-ekosystemu-czechinvest/mapovani-inovacnich-infrastruktur-v-cesku>. [cit. 2024-09-11]

5 Source: National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation of the Czech Republic 2021-2027. Online. 2021. Dostupné z: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.ris3.cz/sites/default/files/National-RIS3-Strategy_2.pdf. [cit. 2024-09-11].

Figure 2: Overview of innovation infrastructure⁶

Legend

- Incubator, accelerator, innovation centre
- Science and technology park
- Coworking
- Open workshop
- Other

Source: Přehled inovační infrastruktury. Online. In: RIS3.cz. Př. n. l. Dostupné z: <https://www.ris3.cz/monitoring/regionalni-dimenze-ris3/inovacni-ekosystemy-v-krajich/mapovani-inovacnich-ekosystemu-czechinvest/mapovani-inovacnich-infrastruktur-v-cesku>. [cit. 2024-09-11].

2.1. Initial mapping

The piloting started with an initial mapping of the activities and actors in the AI ecosystem in Prague. Desk research was the primary source of information. This mapping allowed for the characterisation of the Czech ecosystem in terms of scope, focus areas and actors.

1. Scope⁷: The AI ecosystem in the Czech Republic spans various industries, with significant developments in:

- Healthcare: AI applications for diagnostics, personalized medicine, and hospital management.
- Automotive: Focus on autonomous driving technologies and smart manufacturing processes.

⁶ Source: Přehled inovační infrastruktury. Online. In: RIS3.cz. Př. n. l. Dostupné z: <https://www.ris3.cz/monitoring/regionalni-dimenze-ris3/inovacni-ekosystemy-v-krajich/mapovani-inovacnich-ekosystemu-czechinvest/mapovani-inovacnich-infrastruktur-v-cesku>. [cit. 2024-09-11].

⁷ CzechInvest. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in the Czech Republic: Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

- Finance: Use of AI for risk assessment, fraud detection, and customer service automation.

2. Focus Areas⁸: The main applications identified are the following:

- Natural Language Processing (NLP): Implemented in customer service bots and language translation tools.
- Machine Learning: Used in predictive analytics for various sectors.
- Computer Vision: Applied in surveillance, quality control in manufacturing, and medical imaging.

3. Actors: The key actors active in the ecosystem are:

- Startups⁹:
 - Neurosoft: Specializes in AI-based solutions for healthcare.
 - Sensory: Focuses on AI-driven sensor technologies for various applications.
- Research Institutions¹⁰:
 - Czech Technical University (ČVUT): Engages in cutting-edge AI research and development.
 - Charles University: Focuses on AI in cognitive sciences and machine learning.
- Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic and government initiatives. In this field, it is particularly important to mention the National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence, launched by the Czech Government, which aims to enhance research and foster collaboration between industry and academia¹¹.

3. Collaboration maturity¹²: In terms of the degree of maturity of the collaboration across actors in this ecosystem, several points can be highlighted:

- Partnerships: There are increasing collaborations between universities and industries, particularly in joint research projects and technology transfer initiatives.
- Innovation Clusters: The Czech Republic has established several innovation clusters such as the Czech National Innovation Fund, facilitating cooperation among startups, corporations, and academia.
- Networking Events¹³: Events like the AI Summit Prague and various hackathons encourage knowledge sharing and collaboration among AI professionals and researchers.

The initial mapping and literature review reveals that the ecosystem has some strengths but also some weaknesses that need to be addressed for the ecosystem to be able to flourish.

Strengths: The AI ecosystem in the Czech Republic is vibrant, with a diverse range of actors, applications, and strong government support. The maturity of collaboration between academia and industry is advancing, fostering innovation and practical applications of AI technologies.

- Strong research base¹⁴: The Czech Republic has reputable universities and research institutions (e.g., Charles University, Czech Technical University) that contribute significantly to AI research.

⁸ Hlavačka, J., & Novotný, P. (2021). AI Applications in the Czech Industry. *Journal of Technology and Information*. Retrieved from Journal Website

⁹ Czech Startups. (2023). *Leading AI Startups in the Czech Republic*. Retrieved from Startup Directory.

¹⁰ ČVUT. (2023). *AI Research and Innovation*. Retrieved from ČVUT Website.

¹¹ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. (2023). *National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from Government Portal

¹² CzechInvest. (2022). *Czech National Innovation Fund Report*. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

¹³ AI Summit Prague. (2023). *Event Overview and Insights*. Retrieved from AI Summit Website.

¹⁴ ČVUT. (2023). *AI Research and Innovation*. Retrieved from ČVUT Website.

- Government support¹⁵: The government actively promotes AI through initiatives like the *National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence*, providing funding and resources for research and development.
- A growing startup scene¹⁶: An increasing number of innovative startups are emerging, focusing on diverse applications of AI, particularly in healthcare, finance, and manufacturing.
- Innovation Clusters¹⁷: Collaboration among various stakeholders is fostered through innovation clusters and incubators that encourage knowledge sharing and resource pooling.

Weaknesses: The ecosystem also presents some weaknesses that need to be addressed:

- Limited commercialization¹⁸: Many research projects struggle in the transition from theory to market-ready products, leading to a gap between research and practical application.
- Funding challenges for startups¹⁹: While there is some government support, many startups face difficulties in securing private investment, which can limit their growth and scalability.
- Skills shortage²⁰: There is a notable shortage of skilled professionals in AI and data science, which hampers the ability of companies to expand and innovate.
- Fragmented collaboration²¹: Despite the presence of innovation clusters, collaboration between academia and industry can be inconsistent, with a lack of structured partnerships in some areas.

The Czech Republic's AI ecosystem showcases a robust foundation with strong research capabilities and government support. However, challenges in commercialization, funding, skills availability, and fragmented collaboration need to be addressed to enhance its overall effectiveness and global competitiveness.

2.2. Insights from surveys

A survey was launched in the first half of 2024 to gather insights from the stakeholders active in the AI ecosystem. The results highlight a strong focus on AI across various sectors, with significant support from government and academic institutions. The main challenges revolve around regulatory issues, funding, data management, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Strengthening cooperation through frameworks like ERA Hubs and increasing resource allocation could enhance the Czech AI ecosystem's effectiveness and global integration. Box 1 presents the key insights revealed through the survey.

Box 1: Key insights from the survey

<p>Activities related to AI by Organization:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Union of Industry and Transport: Business support across various sectors, applying AI in manufacturing, workforce management, customer service, analytics, and security. • Prague Innovation Institute: Focus on innovation policy. • Ministry of Industry and Trade (MIT): Oversees the Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (RIS3), coordinates National AI Strategy,
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¹⁵ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. (2023). *National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from Government Portal.

¹⁶ Czech Startups. (2023). *Leading AI Startups in the Czech Republic*. Retrieved from Startup Directory.

¹⁷ CzechInvest. (2022). *Czech National Innovation Fund Report*. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website

¹⁸ Hlavačka, J., & Novotný, P. (2021). *AI Applications in the Czech Industry*. *Journal of Technology and Information*. Retrieved from Journal Website.

¹⁹ CzechInvest. (2022). *Investment Landscape for AI Startups in Czechia*. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

²⁰ Deloitte. (2023). *Workforce Challenges in the AI Sector*. Retrieved from Deloitte Insights.

²¹ Czech National Innovation Fund. (2023). *Collaboration Analysis Report*. Retrieved from Government Portal.

	<p>and supports AI through financial projects and regulatory frameworks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity Hub: Collaborative research and professional services in cybersecurity, founded by three universities. • CTU – Faculty of Information Technology: Basic and applied AI research, focusing on spatio-temporal modeling and weather forecasting. • Recombee: AI product development, specializing in recommender systems and personalized search. • EDIH CTU: Major center for digital innovation in AI/ML, supporting digital transformation across industries.
<p>Key Sectors for AI Systems:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Union of Industry and Transport: Manufacturing, workforce management, customer service, analytics, security. • Ministry of Industry and Trade: AI applications in advanced materials, digitalization, automation, transport, medicine, green technologies, and smart cities. • Cybersecurity Hub: Cybersecurity innovation across various sectors. • CTU: Online services, media, e-commerce, agriculture, urban development. • EDIH CTU: Industry, healthcare, transport, energy, and public sector.
<p>Main Challenges and Needs:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Union of Industry and Transport: Regulatory barriers. • Ministry of Industry and Trade: Need for metrics to evaluate AI initiatives, financial resources, data governance, interdisciplinary collaboration, and adapting international AI ethics and principles. • Cybersecurity Hub: Regulation challenges. • CTU Researchers: Need for more computing resources (GPUs), funding for AI research, and support for company-university collaborations. • EDIH CTU: Complex issues involving finance, policy development, data management, and scalability.
<p>Cooperation in the AI Ecosystem:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Union of Industry and Transport: Effective consultation system via AI platform. • Ministry of Industry and Trade: Works through AI Committee and Digitalisation Platform to coordinate National AI Strategy and digital transformation efforts. • CTU: Connected ecosystem, co-founded prg.ai.
<p>Suggestions for Improvement:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Union of Industry and Transport: Expand knowledge and networks. • Ministry of Industry and Trade: Holistic collaboration across the AI value chain and leveraging ERA Hubs for European networking and resource sharing.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CTU: Fund long-term AI challenges. • EDIH CTU: Knowledge sharing, service partnerships, and joint training activities.
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Another survey with an exclusive focus on companies was also distributed. The results of the survey revealed that organizations like InovecTech are heavily involved in AI innovation, particularly in manufacturing and logistics. InovecTech's key initiative is the development of 'SW sensors,' an AI-powered solution for collecting and analyzing visual data to optimize manufacturing processes. Their approach addresses the need for flexible, affordable data collection tools to digitize the shop floor quickly. The main sectors applying AI include manufacturing and logistics, emphasizing real-time data processing and process optimization.

The challenges identified by the respondents include the high cost of AI expertise and innovation capital, with financing difficulties exacerbated by high-interest rates on loans and low valuations for equity investments. Regulatory and technical barriers also pose significant hurdles. Collaboration within the AI ecosystem is active but can be improved by introducing verified solutions at marketplaces, offering discounts for trade fair presentations, and establishing investment funds for high-potential AI innovation projects. The ERA Hubs concept is seen as beneficial, providing a platform for better resource sharing and cross-regional cooperation.

The results of the survey highlighted the following recommendations to develop the AI Czech ecosystem:

- Improve **access to financing:**
 - Develop targeted financial instruments and investment funds to support AI innovations with favourable terms.
 - Increase transparency and accessibility of R&D grants to ensure funds reach high-potential projects.
- Enhance **collaboration platforms:**
 - Implement verified solution marketplaces and offer financial incentives for participation in industry events.
 - Foster partnerships between startups, established companies, and research institutions to leverage collective expertise and resources.
- Address **regulatory and technical barriers:**
 - Simplify regulatory processes to reduce the burden on AI innovators.
 - Provide technical support and resources to overcome data quality and infrastructure challenges.

Participants indicated in the survey that by addressing these areas, the Czech Republic can strengthen its AI ecosystem, promote innovation, and enhance its global competitiveness in AI technology.

2.3. Insights from the roundtable

A roundtable was organized on the 22nd of March 2024. The participants included representatives from the Ministry of Industry and Trade, the Confederation of Industry of the Czech Republic, Prague.AI, CzechInvest, Prague Innovation Institute, Cybersecurity Hub, Transfera.cz, ICT Union, South Bohemia University, and others, as well as TUE, IDEA, DTU Skylab, CTU from the COOPERATE project side.

The discussions highlighted the need for clear definitions, focused objectives, and streamlined processes to make ERA Hubs effective. There was consensus on the importance of integrating existing initiatives, ensuring proper funding, and fostering collaboration across regions and sectors to drive innovation and economic growth. Box 2 shows the main discussion points and conclusions.

Box 2: Main conclusions of the roundtable on the ERA Hub definition and scope

- **Geographical Boundaries:** They vary by region, as seen with Brainport Eindhoven versus Science City Lyngby in Denmark. Each region must self-define its own ERA Hub boundaries.
- **Existing Initiatives:** There is a need to map existing European initiatives to understand ERA Hub's unique value, focusing on knowledge transfer within regional ecosystems.
- **Value Addition and Differentiation:** ERA Hubs aim to bridge gaps between current initiatives, emphasizing cross-regional knowledge transfer and collaboration within the quadruple helix (academia, industry, government, and civil society).
- **Feedback and Positioning:** Continuous feedback is sought to position ERA Hubs uniquely at the European level, ensuring they do not duplicate existing efforts but rather complement and enhance them.
- **Challenges and Ambiguities:** Concerns about duplication with existing regional strategies (e.g., RIS3 strategy) and unclear added value.
- **Complexity of bureaucratic processes and funding mechanisms.** Importance of integrating well-functioning ecosystems and avoiding unnecessary layers of complexity.
- **Examples and Comparisons:**
 - Canada's AI Centers shows a holistic approach integrating research, application, and industry collaboration.
 - Science City Lyngby (Denmark) illustrates the importance of government and regional funding, the collaboration with private sector, and the establishment of neutral collaboration spaces.
- **Barriers and Cooperation:**
 - The identified barriers include the lack of AI experts, low-quality datasets, regulatory challenges, and fragmented activities.
 - Encouraging cooperation between ecosystem actors to address these barriers and enhance overall innovation capacity is needed.
- **Strategic Goals:**
 - Supporting the entire R&D&I chain from basic research to product development.
 - Enhancing education and training to address the shortage of skilled personnel.
 - Aligning with national and regional innovation strategies to ensure cohesive development.
- **Practical Implementation:** Emphasis on practical solutions and collaboration, leveraging feedback and ongoing evaluations to refine ERA Hub concepts.

2.4. Final workshop

At the COOPERATE General Assembly in June 2024, we organized a roundtable with stakeholders from the university, government representatives and company representatives and a participant from the EIT. Together with the COOPERATE team and two guest speakers, there were 27 people in the workshop.

Figure 3: Participants in the final workshop

Source: COOPERATE project.

The workshop participants discussed the revised definition and positioning of ERA Hubs. In order to set the right expectations and context, we first listened to a lecture by Maarten Steibuch from the Technical University of Eindhoven on how their ecosystem works, how they have managed to turn the classical structures between commercial, academic and governmental spheres into a functional system that benefits everyone while generating considerable funding for science and research as well as projects with an impact on society as a whole in specific regions. This was followed by a lecture by Jan Urban, representative of CTU, on increasing the relevance and the competitiveness of the Czech science and research. These two lectures offered a beautiful contrast over the development of two physically not so distant ecosystems, but they pointed out that there is a difference in the development of relationships and in the thinking of stakeholders.

On the Czech side, the obstacles mentioned above from the perspective of the state and companies were confirmed. This was linked to what was perceived as a dysfunctional transfer of technology, information and people, areas on which there is little tradition in the Czech Republic. Participants stressed that there is a long way to go to set up functional procedures, quality financing, producing results and ideally also returns, and also creating an attractive environment for companies and foreign experts.

2.5. Conclusion of the piloting activities in the Czech ecosystem

On the basis of the activities carried out within the piloting phase in Czechia, it can be inferred that establishing an ERA Hub in the Czech Republic is recommended due to its potential to enhance collaboration, support commercialization, and improve funding access. To be truly effective, the Hub must focus on clear governance, tailored funding strategies, and commercialization pathways that address the unique challenges of the Czech AI ecosystem. With these elements, ERA Hubs can drive significant innovation and economic growth in the region. The analysis of the information gathered in the diverse activities throughout the pilot indicates that establishing an ERA Hub in the Czech Republic offers significant advantages but also highlights areas that need refinement to maximize its impact.

Among the key benefits of establishing an ERA Hub, we can find the following:

1. **Enhancing collaboration and governance:** The Czech AI ecosystem boasts strong research capabilities and numerous startups, but collaboration between academia, industry, and government is often fragmented. An ERA Hub would formalize collaboration, aligning goals and resources across these sectors.

Example: ČVUT conducts advanced AI research but lacks streamlined pathways to partner with industry for commercialization. The ERA Hub's co-creation and governance focus can bridge these gaps, fostering a more cohesive and innovative ecosystem.

2. **Addressing commercialization challenges:** Despite robust academic output, Czech AI innovations often struggle to reach the market due to limited support and funding. An ERA Hub could facilitate commercialization by offering targeted mentoring, funding access, and knowledge transfer.

Example: Startups like Neurosoft, which develop AI-driven healthcare solutions, could benefit from ERA Hub support, moving their innovations from prototype to market readiness.

3. **Leveraging funding and investment opportunities:** The ERA Hubs framework improves access to EU and regional funding, essential for scaling AI innovations. Establishing an ERA Hub would help Czech ecosystems qualify for broader funding programs, addressing critical financial shortages.

Example: ERA Hubs could streamline access to dedicated AI funds from the EU, tackling the lack of early-stage investment faced by Czech startups.

4. **Fostering talent development and mobility:** The Czech AI sector suffers from a skills shortage, hindering growth. An ERA Hub's emphasis on talent development, training, and mobility would expand the skills base, supporting companies in attracting and retaining top talent.

Example: ERA Hubs could facilitate training exchanges between Czech institutions and mature European ecosystems, directly addressing local skill gaps.

Among the challenges and areas for improvement, the following ones were stressed:

1. **Need for clear governance and strategic vision:** For an ERA Hub to be effective, it needs a well-defined governance structure that aligns local interests with European goals. The current lack of strategic coordination in the Czech AI ecosystem could reduce the Hub's effectiveness if not addressed.
2. **Focus on commercialization pathways:** The ERA Hubs framework needs more specific tools and guidance tailored to commercialization in the Czech context. Without this focus, research may remain stuck in labs without making it to market.
3. **Tailored funding solutions:** To fully support Czech AI startups, ERA Hubs must offer funding mechanisms specifically designed for their needs, including AI commercialization grants and seed funding.

In this context, the next question to be answered is **how the ERA Hubs framework and tools can help the Czech AI ecosystem to grow**. The ERA Hubs framework and its tools offer valuable support mechanisms that align well with the needs of the Czech AI ecosystem, particularly in terms of governance and collaboration. However, tailored enhancements, including specific funding programs and detailed commercialization strategies, are needed to fully address the challenges faced by Czech AI actors. Translating these into actionable EU policies would significantly boost the growth and maturity of the Czech AI ecosystem. The following steps would be required:

1. **Adaptability of the ERA Hub definition and framework to the Czech AI ecosystem:** The ERA Hubs framework is adaptable and designed to support ecosystems of varying maturity, making it relevant for the Czech AI landscape, which includes a mix of advanced research institutions and emerging startups. The framework's seven lines of action provide a structured approach that can address several specific challenges in the Czech AI ecosystem.

Example of adaptability: The Czech AI ecosystem, centered around institutions like ČVUT and a growing number of AI startups, benefits significantly from the ERA Hub's focus on co-creation arenas and governance strategies. These provide a platform for structured interactions between academia, industry, and government—key areas where the Czech AI ecosystem is currently developing but still faces challenges in translating research into commercial applications.

Specific fit: The framework's emphasis on governance can directly support the Czech ecosystem's need for better structured and consistent collaboration models, which are currently fragmented. However, while the framework supports broad-based collaboration, it may need more specific guidance tailored to AI commercialisation, which remains a challenge in Czechia.

2. **Usefulness and completeness of the tools (Playbook and Toolbox) for the Czech AI ecosystem:** The Playbook and Toolbox provide facilitation materials and methodologies that can help guide Czech AI actors in establishing effective ERA Hubs, particularly in areas like governance, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer. However, specific challenges within the Czech AI ecosystem highlight potential gaps in these tools:

Example of usefulness: The Playbook's guidelines on establishing governance structures can help Czech research institutions like ČVUT implement more robust models for managing

partnerships with startups and industries. This can address current weaknesses in aligning academic research with industry needs, which is crucial for effective AI commercialization.

Example of missing elements: While the Playbook provides general facilitation strategies, it lacks detailed modules on tackling funding challenges, a significant barrier for Czech AI startups. For instance, Neurosoft, a Czech AI startup, struggles with securing sufficient private investment to scale its solutions. Including specific strategies within the Toolbox for accessing diverse funding sources or leveraging public-private partnerships could directly address this need.

3. **Needs in terms of EU-Level policies relevant to the Czech AI ecosystem:** The ERA Hub initiative identifies several needs at the EU level that could translate into policy recommendations tailored to the specific context of Czechia's AI ecosystem:

Enhanced funding mechanisms: Czech AI startups face significant hurdles in securing funding. An EU-level policy could include creating targeted funding programs specifically designed for AI commercialization. For instance, the Czech AI ecosystem would benefit from a dedicated European AI commercialization fund that directly addresses early-stage funding gaps, encouraging risk-taking and innovation in Czech startups.

Skills development: The Czech AI ecosystem has a noted skills shortage, particularly in advanced AI and data science expertise. EU-level policies that fund cross-border AI talent development programs, such as specialized AI training exchanges between Czech institutions like ČVUT and more mature ecosystems in countries like Denmark, could help address this gap.

Standardized governance and best practices: The ERA Hub's goal of establishing standardized governance structures could be particularly beneficial for Czech AI actors, who currently operate under varied and sometimes conflicting governance models. EU policy should push for a harmonized set of best practices that ensure more seamless collaboration between Czech universities, startups, and industry.

Example of policy translation: By advocating for standardized governance frameworks at the EU level, Czech AI ecosystems can align their practices with leading European hubs, thereby enhancing intra-operability and facilitating smoother, more productive collaborations. This can directly support the integration of AI innovations into the market, which is currently hampered by inconsistent partnership structures in Czechia.

3. Exploring and validating the interregional collaboration dimension of the ERA Hubs framework

This section presents the main findings related to interregional collaboration, one of the pillars of the ERA Hubs framework. The structure of this chapter is as follows:

1. First, the chapter presents the results of an analysis of the thematic specialisation and potential for collaboration across Phase 1 pilot regions. This includes the analysis of the themes and specialisations across the three main technical universities present in each region.
2. Second, the chapter shows the results of the analysis of collaboration patterns between the three countries at EU level. This analysis focuses on the participation of actors coming from the three countries in projects funded by the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation.
3. Finally, the chapter concludes with an in-depth case study on stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration focusing on the collaboration between Brainport (The Netherlands) and Lyngby (Denmark).

3.1. Thematic specialisation

Collaborating across regional innovation ecosystems with a focus on thematic specialisation can significantly boost the development of new technologies, industries, and solutions. From the perspective of the potential for collaboration, the analysis shows the extent to which the universities present in each of the ecosystems have some degree of thematic overlap. From the viewpoint of the potential for collaboration, the COOPERATE team has developed an in-depth analysis of the expertise of the Universities/Regions in the three ecosystems based on patents and publications. This is based on university output, comparison university output, patent analysis (country level), and patent analysis (region level).

Figure 4 shows the thematic overlap stemming from the analysis of patents and publications. In terms of patent output, it can be observed that the three institutions produce significant outputs in the fields of mechanical engineering (lighting), electric techniques/elements, climate change technologies and medical and veterinary science health. In terms of scientific publications, the output of the three institutions show interesting overlaps in the fields of artificial intelligence, composite materials, environmental sciences and chemical engineering.

Figure 4: Thematic overlap

Source: LENS.org

Table 1 shows the overlap between the different knowledge institutions and their strengths in the different themes, measured by scientific output (publications). The themes artificial intelligence, composite materials, environmental sciences and chemical engineering show a strong overlap between the different universities. On the other hand, the areas of telecommunications, machine learning and biomedical engineering present the smallest overlap.

Table 1: Degree of overlap

	Theme	TU/e	TUD	CTU
Basic themes	Computer Science	2091	2444	699
	Materials Science	1709	2363	925
	Physics	1039	1653	773
	Chemistry	978	2374	220
	Medicine	839	1028	156
	Engineering	724	1123	283
	Mathematics	632	734	375
	Biology	456	2097	95
Specialized themes	Artificial Intelligence	582	521	180
	Psychology	483	290	0
	Chemical Engineering	477	609	72
	Compositie Material	443	661	396
	Nanotechnology	385	396	0
	Organic Chemistry	351	703	66
	Quantum mechanics	333	502	126
	Optoelectronics	318	346	105
	Mechanics	315	322	92
	Optics	270	440	196
	Internal Medicine	261	343	156
	Catalysis	237	404	0
	Biochemistry	214	740	0
	Machine Learning	171	0	0
	Biomedical engineering	147	0	0
	Electrical Engineering	139	296	48
	Environmental Science	134	1190	169
	Telecommunications	126	0	0
	Ecology	0	510	0
	Geology	0	530	92
		6425	11162	2837

Source: LENS.org

3.2. Cross regional collaboration under the EU Framework Programmes

The analysis also included a second perspective: the analysis of the outputs and patterns of the collaborations involving the Danish and Dutch ecosystems. This departs from the analysis of all public research projects funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe framework programme for research and innovation from 2021 to 2027. Data have been collected from the CORDIS database²². In addition to the details of Horizon Europe projects (funding program, cost, topic, etc.), the database also includes information on the organisations involved in these projects (name, role, country, city, etc.).

²² <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects>

General overview

The CORDIS database provides information on a total of 10147 projects with 20331 distinct organisations involved. As displayed in the figure below, the countries hosting the majority of organisations involved in Horizon Europe projects are Germany (10.6%), followed by Spain (10.0%), France (8.7%) and Italy (8.6%). All other countries are less well represented in the sample.

Figure 5: Geographical distribution of the organisations involved in Horizon Europe projects

Source: COOPERATE project based on CORDIS data.

Dutch and Danish organisations account for 5.8% and 2.0% of the total number of distinct organisations involved in Horizon Europe projects. On average, Dutch organisations are involved in 3.6 projects and the Dutch organisation involved in the highest number of projects (247) is Delft University of Technology. Similarly, Danish organisations are on average involved in 3.9 projects. The most active organisation in Denmark is Copenhagen University with 256 projects in which it is involved.

Turning to the projects, the analysis reveals that out of the 10147 Horizon Europe projects, 1160 involve at least one Danish organisation and 2458 involve at least a Dutch organisation. As displayed in the table below, most Dutch organisations are based in Amsterdam (16.9%), Utrecht (9.4%), Delft (8.9%), and Eindhoven (6.9%). In Denmark, most organisations are based in Copenhagen (25.7%), followed by Lyngby (15.3%), Aarhus (14.3%) and Aalborg (6.8%).

Table 2: Top 10 cities in the Netherlands and in Denmark in which most organisations are based

Netherlands		Denmark	
Amsterdam	16.9%	Copenhagen	25.7%
Utrecht	9.4%	Lyngby	15.3%
Delft	8.9%	Aarhus	14.3%
Eindhoven	6.9%	Aalborg	6.8%
Wageningen	6.6%	Odense	4.3%
Den Haag	5.0%	Hillerod	2.6%
Leiden	4.9%	Taastrup	1.8%
Enschede	4.2%	Frederiksberg	1.8%

Netherlands		Denmark	
Groningen	4.2%	Roskilde	1.4%
Nijmegen	4.2%	Vejle	0.9%

Source: COOPERATE project based on CORDIS data.

Collaborations between Dutch and Danish organisations

As a second step, the analysis zooms in on Horizon Europe projects which involve at least one Dutch and one Danish organisation. This step provides some preliminary insights on the collaborative efforts between organisations based in these two countries. As showed in the figure below, out of 10147 Horizon Europe projects, 457 involve at least one Dutch and one Danish organisations. Out of these, 121 have either a Dutch (69) or Danish (52) organisation as project coordinator. The average number of organisations per project is 22 with a minimum of 2 and a maximum of 199.

Figure 6: Zoom in on projects involving Dutch and Danish organisations

Source: COOPERATE project based on CORDIS data.

To further narrow down the analysis, certain projects have been further investigated. More specifically, collaborations involving the Dutch and Danish organisations involved in the COOPERATE project have been examined in more details. The analysis reveals that:

- There are 93 projects involving the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and a Dutch partner. The most represented Dutch partners for DTU are Delft University of Technology (14), Wageningen University & Research (13), TU/e (11) and Utrecht University (8).
- There is 1 project involving Science City Lyngby and a Dutch partner. This is the COOPERATE project which involves Science City Lyngby and DTU in Denmark and TU/e and Brainport in the Netherlands.
- There are 31 projects involving the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) and a Danish partner. The most represented Danish partners for TU/e are DTU (11 projects), Aalborg University (6 projects) and Copenhagen University (4).
- There are 2 projects involving Brainport and a Danish partner. These are Aalborg University (1 project), Foreningen Made (1 project) and the two partners of the COOPERATE project (DTU and Science City Lyngby)

- Finally, there are 11 projects involving at least one of the two Dutch organisations (either TU/e or Brainport) and at least of one the two Danish organisations (either DTU or Science City Lyngby). The table below lists all the Dutch and Danish organisations involved in these projects.

Table 3: List of Dutch and Danish organisations involved in projects with either TU/e or Brainport and either DTU or Science City Lyngby

Dutch organisations	Danish organisations
FuseNet	Syddansk University
Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)	Aarhus University
University of Amsterdam	Aalborg University
NXP Semiconductors Netherlands BV	Ofs Fitel Denmark ApS
European Nutrition for Health Alliance Foundation	Eldan Recycling A/S
European Federation of Associations of Dietitians (EFAD)	LM Wind Power
University of Twente	Alea Quantum Technologies ApS
HyCC B.V.	Siphotonic ApS
Q* Bird BV	NKT Photonics A/S
Delft University of Technology	
Bright Photonics BV	
Smart Photonics BV	

Source: COOPERATE project.

3.3. Stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration: the case of the Brainport – Lyngby collaboration

The goal of analyses presented below is to validate the ERA Hubs framework specifically in the interregional dimension and therefore to use the insights gathered to improve the interregional dimension of the model.

To enhance interregional collaboration the pilot explored the concept of stakeholder engagement and aimed to improve this within this context. Enhanced engagement can lead stakeholders to more actively participate and contribute towards developing research and innovation in the collaborations (Widén et al., 2014). Correspondingly, an example of pragmatic aim of stakeholder engagement is to “seek to establish and maintain functioning relationships for organisational and societal change” (Kujala et al., 2022). This can therefore inspire collaborative activities like interregional collaborations in this context (Kujala et al., 2022).

The concept of stakeholder engagement is rapidly changing in the literature. We have used the multidimensional conceptualization of engagement, focusing on the cognitive, emotional and behavioural dimension (Jonas et al., 2018). First, the cognitive dimension was defined as a person’s degree of awareness or mindset towards in this case interregional collaborations. Second, the emotional dimension was characterized by the personal feeling towards these collaborations (Jonas et al., 2018). Lastly, the behavioural dimension was described as the continued process and level of energy involved in interacting in these collaborations (Jonas et al., 2018). This conceptualization, therefore, extends beyond just the participation in these collaborations as it also encompasses the mindset and feelings towards this topic as well as the continued effort displayed.

There is value in using the quadruple helix framework to categorize groups of stakeholders to better understand their specific needs and challenges regarding stakeholder engagement. The quadruple helix framework was therefore used in this pilot as a lens to look through when looking at the problem of improving stakeholder engagement in interregional collaborations.

As such we elaborate the following overarching research question: **How does stakeholder engagement unfold in interregional collaborations?**

Approach and framework to the analysis

This chapter follows a case study design, where the Brainport region is the case that will be analysed to build a better understanding of stakeholder engagement within interregional collaborations.

The case study comprises four phases, as illustrated in Figure 7. In the first phase, a mapping of the level of collaboration between the Brainport region and the Lyngby region was conducted. This quantitative analysis served to complement the main research by providing data on the level of collaboration already existing between these regions. By identifying active quadruple helix stakeholder types and potential gaps, this analysis provided valuable insights into the landscape of the collaboration between these regions. These insights can, for example, be used to justify the need to improve the engagement of specific types of stakeholders. In the second phase, a preliminary model based on existing stakeholder engagement literature was developed. The existing literature covers stakeholder engagement in various contexts; however, the interregional collaboration context is missing. The preliminary model serves to provide initial insights into factors that could potentially also be relevant to stakeholder engagement in the interregional collaboration context. However, this is not enough to draw conclusions about stakeholder engagement in interregional collaborations as these factors are not found in research in this context. Consequently, in the third phase, qualitative research complemented and partially validated the preliminary model made in the second phase. The qualitative research, including interviews, gained insights into factors impacting stakeholder engagement specifically in interregional collaborations. In the fourth phase, the insights from the interviews were combined with those from the literature, creating a comprehensive model tailored to stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration. Based on this model insights were drawn on how to improve the stakeholder engagement for the specific types of stakeholders in interregional collaborations.

Figure 7: Four phases of the Dutch pilot

Source: COOPERATE project.

Insights from mapping

In the mapping of the collaboration landscape local boundaries for Brainport and Lyngby were used that were identified by Brainport Development and Science City Lyngby respectively.

- The following 21 municipalities were identified as part of the Brainport region: Asten, Bergeijk, Best, Bladel, Cranendonck, Deurne, Eersel, Eindhoven, Geldrop-Mierlo, Gemert-Bakel, Heeze-Leende, Helmond, Laarbeek, Nuenen, Oirschot, Reusel-De Mierden, Someren, Son en Breugel, Valkenswaard, and Veldhoven.

- The following 20 municipalities were identified as part of the Lyngby or the Greater Copenhagen region: Albertslund, Ballerup, Brøndby, Dragør, Frederiksberg, Furesø, Gentofte, Gladsaxe, Glostrup, Greve, Herlev, Hvidovre, Høje-Taastrup, Ishøj, Københavns, Lyngby-Taarbæk, Rudersdal, Rødovre, Tårnby, and Vallensbæk.

First, it is evident that the academic institutions are the backbone of this interregional connection. There is a good collaborative connection between the academic institutions themselves through co-publications, as there were 268 co-publications retrieved from The Lens database. Figure 5 illustrates the types of scholarly works published by authors affiliated with Brainport and Lyngby over time. The data reveals that journal articles are the predominant outcome of these collaborations. The number of co-publications increased steadily from 2015 to 2020, after which it stabilized. There were two types of collaborations identified by this search. Some publications were co-authored by a professor from Brainport and one from Lyngby, while others were written by an author that is affiliated with institutions from both regions. These dual-affiliated authors act as bridges between the institutions of the regions and are therefore seen as an interregional collaboration. Additionally, academic institutions are by far the more active collaborators (in terms of number of participations) in the Horizon Europe projects in both regions. The latter reflects the commitment of the universities to and the understanding of the benefits of interregional collaborations with various quadruple helix stakeholders. This suggests that academic institutes could act as promoters of these kinds of collaborations, inspiring other organisations within their region to engage in them.

Second, the industry helix is also well-represented in the collaboration landscape. From the Horizon Europe data, it can be drawn that there is a relatively high number of different Industry collaborators in Brainport, especially compared to the other types of actors, as can also be seen in Figure 8. Several companies have a presence in both regions, with their headquarters in one of them and a branch in the other. However, it is noteworthy that the industry organizations active in Horizon Europe projects tend to participate in only a limited number of projects, unlike their academic counterparts. To address this, it might be valuable to invest in strategies to keep these organizations engaged and satisfied throughout the projects, thereby motivating them to participate in more collaborations.

Third, the data revealed only a limited representation of civil society and government stakeholder in the collaboration between Brainport and Lyngby. For example, in the Brainport region there were only five civil society collaborators contributing to five Horizon Europe projects, and no government collaborators were identified. The ACHILLES database also showed no level of government type collaboration and there was no further civil society collaboration data collected. The government and civil society stakeholders located in Brainport, therefore, appear to be underrepresented in the interregional collaborations between Brainport and Lyngby based on the data collected in this research.

Figure 8: Scholarly works published over time

Source: The Lens Database.

Figure 9: Horizon Europe collaborators from the Brainport area

Source: COOPERATE project based on CORDIS data.

Stakeholders consulted

In the qualitative phase of this research, 11 interviews were conducted with representatives from 7 distinct organisations. Three representatives were interviewed for each component of the quadruple helix, except for civil society where only two participants were found.

Of the participants, 8 were male (73%) and 3 were female (27%). The participants were selected based on their involvement in Horizon Europe projects, which were identified using the Cordis data during the first phase. These projects represented an interregional collaboration between the Brainport and Lyngby regions. Notably, the participants from the government helix were not identified through the Cordis data, as the data did not present any governmental organisations that were involved in the Horizon Europe projects. Instead, the participants from this helix were found through connections established by partners of the COOPERATE project. Table 4 presents the demographics of the interviewees.

Table 4: Interviewees' demographics

Participant's ID	Gender	Organisation	Quadruple helix type
1	Male	Municipality of Eindhoven	Government
2	Male	Games for Health	Industry
3	Male	SMART Photonics	Industry
4	Female	Province of North-Brabant	Government
5	Male	Philips Electronics	Industry
6	Male	Brainport Development	Civil Society
7	Male	Brainport Development	Civil Society
8	Female	Municipality of Eindhoven	Government
9	Male	Eindhoven University of Technology	Academia
10	Male	Eindhoven University of Technology	Academia
11	Female	Eindhoven University of Technology	Academia

Source: COOPERATE project.

Main insights gathered

To gain a deeper understanding of stakeholder engagement in the context of interregional collaborations, 11 semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives from various quadruple helix stakeholders. The goal of these interviews was to identify factors that influence stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration based on participants' experiences in these kinds of collaborations. The data collected from the interviews were systematically coded, with some codes directly representing specific factors, while others were grouped to form a broader category of factors. These factors were then organized into overarching themes. The themes and factors identified by the participants are summarized in Figure 10. In this model, links and factors in blue depict those that were also identified in the literature during the second phase of this study, while those in green depict the new contributions from the qualitative data. The arrows indicate the impact of each theme on the dimensions of stakeholder engagement, while the dashed lines represent connections between the themes.

Figure 10: Qualitative model from Dutch pilot including significant linkages between themes

Source: COOPERATE project.

1. The first significant theme that emerged from the analysis is **the way an organisation perceives interregional collaborations**, particularly the importance of these collaborations and the partners involved.
 - i. The most frequently identified factor within this theme was **resource dependency**: the organisation found interregional collaborations important as it felt it was dependent on resources it could gain through these kinds of collaborations. The resources sought by organisations in these collaborations ranged from specific expertise to capacity and influence. Organisations perceive to be dependent on others and their resources, which influences an organisation's motivation to participate in interregional collaborations. This resource dependency primarily impacts the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement as it influences the perception of these collaborations and an organisation's motivation to participate.
 - ii. The second most frequently identified factor within this theme are the **expectations of partners**, where it was found that both positive and negative expectations from specific partners could influence their motivation to participate in current or future interregional projects. This factor therefore impacts the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - iii. The third factor identified relates to the **organisational strategy**, particularly in how organisations perceive interregional collaborations. This influence can be expressed through leadership, the long-term vision of the organisation, and the recognition of potential learning opportunities from these collaborations. Leadership perspectives can therefore influence an organisation's motivation to participate in interregional collaborations, impacting the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement. It can also occur that the impact of an organisation's strategy is demonstrated through the time and capacity availability that an organisation allocates to these kinds of collaborations. Time and capacity availability can impact an organisation's ability to stay engaged throughout a project, thereby impacting the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.
2. The second significant theme that emerged from the data is **communication, encompassing both the dissemination of certain important information and the structure of communication between partners**.
 - i. The first factor that was identified within this theme to impact stakeholder engagement is **continuous communication**, particularly as it helps partners stay connected to each other and the project. Especially in large, interregional collaborations where the absence of regular, informal interactions can make it challenging for partners to stay in touch with each other's activities and the project. Continuous communication was found to be crucial to ensure alignment and continued engagement throughout the project, thereby influencing the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - ii. **Face-to-face communication** was also identified within this theme in connection to continuous communication, as the benefits of face-to-face, as opposed to online interactions to sustain stakeholder engagement, were often highlighted by participants. Face-to-face communication fosters personal connections and facilitates cross-learning, as demonstrated by the quote below, thereby impacting the continued effort of partners during the collaboration. Face-to-face communication, therefore, positively influences the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - iii. The third factor identified within this theme is to **'level the playing field' early in the collaboration**. In large interregional collaborations, partners often come from diverse organisational backgrounds, each with different levels of knowledge and distinct ways of working. Participants noted the necessity of getting everyone on the same level in terms of way of working and knowledge early in the project to ensure consistent engagement, promote cross-learning

and prevent misunderstandings. By levelling the playing field early in the project, partners are more likely to remain engaged, thereby stimulating the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.

- iv. The fourth factor identified within this theme is **clarity on the benefits**, clear communication of the benefits associated with participation enhances the motivation of all partners involved. By continually emphasizing the added value of participation, clarity on the benefits impacts the behavioural and cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement.
- v. The fifth factor is **clarity on the roles**: well-defined roles and the associated responsibilities contribute to sustained engagement throughout the project, by keeping partners consistently aware of their tasks and obligations. The clarity on the roles, therefore, impacts the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement, ensuring constant involvement and commitment to the project and its goals.

“I also see that especially when being face to face, which does not happen so often due to the interregional aspect, that those engaged discussions that is where you see that that cross learning takes place and cross understanding. There you also see that with online meetings you often are limited in time and then you really more focus on the content. So, you see that relationship building being less and then you see that the face-to-face meetings are actually every time where that the bonding gets better. Because then you happen to suddenly have that conversation with somebody, some other party in the Helix that had some more time to discuss what you just mentioned about some topic that you are interested in or also struggle with in the company. Then you get a more in-depth conversation which you don’t get online. So, I would almost say that the more time you invest in the beginning face to face the better it is. Which is why that first year may be crucial.”

3. The third significant theme that emerged from the data is **goal alignment, which refers to the alignment between the goals of the project and those of the partners involved**.
 - i. The first factor identified is the **alignment with the organisation’s goals and needs**. Interregional collaborations often involve a diverse set of partners, each with distinct goals and needs that must be met for them to be motivated to participate. The project should align with the organisational goals of the partners involved to create tangible value for these organisations. The alignment of the project with these individual goals is crucial for stimulating the motivation to participate, thereby impacting the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - ii. The second factor identified within this theme is **the presence of a common goal**. A common goal was found to be crucial to prevent partners from focusing solely on their own organisational objectives and therefore losing engagement for the overall project goals, as demonstrated by the quote below. A shared project goal can sustain engagement throughout a project by keeping everyone’s focus on the same goal, thus preventing silo mentality and stimulating the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement. Continuous communication was found to be able to support the alignment with this common goal by keeping the partners closely connected. Shared goals should be realistic to avoid disappointment and negative feelings, thereby impacting the emotional dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - iii. Lastly, it was noted that **aligning plans and projects with the current efforts** of a project can help sustain engagement. Discussing plans and subsequent steps beyond the current project can keep the partners interested and invested in the collaboration. This approach can therefore impact the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.

“I think and then here maybe it can be biased because of a sustainability and circularity related topic, that in this case you see that there is a kind of common interest, a common goal. So I really also see that it ties in very much with personal engagement for people who all feel that we have a bit of a mission to do something with circularity. So, that common goal and in DICE we see that very specifically because it is there, but that helps. Therefore, the drive is also there and that is also what I can see when we are together the topic of sustainability also ties the people together.”

4. The fourth significant theme that emerged from the data relates to **factors related to the governance of interregional collaborations**, which are factors concerning structures, mechanisms or processes that guide the management and direction of these collaborations.
 - i. The most frequently identified factor within this theme was **the role of the project leader**. It was found that a project leader who focuses not only on the content but also on the way partners are collaborating is crucial to facilitate an effective collaboration, as demonstrated by the quote below. Furthermore, the interviewees indicated that the approach to the role of a project leader was often reliant on the person or organisation fulfilling this role. Some leaders were proficient at facilitating and stimulating collaboration, while others focused solely on the content of the project. This crucial role could be fulfilled either by the project coordinator or through a dedicated supportive position, such as a project management office. Such a supportive position could be set up to complement the project coordinator by focusing solely on supporting and guiding the collaboration. By facilitating and guiding the way partners collaborate, the role of a project leader therefore impacts the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - ii. The second factor identified within this theme is **bureaucratic burden**. Interviewees highlighted the amount of paperwork associated with interregional collaborations to be a bureaucratic burden negatively impacting their motivation to participate in these collaborations. By negatively influencing the motivation of organisations to participate in interregional collaborations, these kinds of bureaucratic burdens impact the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - iii. The last factor identified within this theme is **the need for a structure for communication**. It was found that to sustain engagement, structures must be set up to facilitate communication and collaboration between the partners of a collaboration. By establishing a communication structure to support the collaboration, the communication between partners is enhanced and the formation of common goals is facilitated. By supporting continuous communication and goal alignment, a communication structure impacts the behavioural dimension of stakeholder engagement.

“I think that's an interesting point here because I think in our case, we have a very engaged coordinator who is also really open for this perspective. I think one of the risks, especially in technology development projects, is delivering on the content. But I think the coordinator has a crucial role to not only focus on the content delivery but also especially enabling the collaboration perspective. So to be open for that.

The coordinator is very often a content specialist or at least very close to the topic. And you might say that it would be good to have maybe the coordinator or the PMO or a kind of central role also be very much into this collaboration perspective and the facilitation of the collaboration.”

5. The fifth theme that emerged from the data is **factors related to the network and the networking capabilities of an organisation**.
 - i. The first factor identified within this theme is **the size and strength of an organisation's network**. The prospect of networking opportunities to grow their current network was found to motivate organisations to participate in interregional collaborations. In addition, the current size and strength of an organisation's network were also found to affect the motivation to participate. Participants indicated that involvement in collaborations was often reliant on existing connections. Organisations with larger networks are more frequently invited to participate in interregional collaborations, and, when invited, their motivation is often high due to their familiarity with other involved organisations. This effect on motivation can be seen as an upward spiral as larger networks will lead to familiarity with more organisations leading to more motivation to participate in these kinds of collaborations. By stimulating the motivation to participate this factor primarily impacts the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - ii. The second factor identified within this theme is related to **relationship-building skills**, which refer to the required abilities to build and maintain relationships in a network and project. Interviewees noted that especially in interregional collaborations there are a lot of challenges when collaborating due to cultural differences and different organisational backgrounds. It was found that cultural awareness and an open mindset are crucial skills to sustain engagement of all partners involved and to prevent other partners from developing negative feelings towards partners or the collaboration itself. Furthermore, interregional collaborations often involve organisations from both developed and less-developed countries. In such instances, organisations from the less-developed countries can sometimes be treated as less capable or knowledgeable by organisations from the developed countries. These abilities are crucial to prevent negative feelings from being developed by partners and to maintain engagement throughout the project. These relationship-building skills, therefore, impact the emotional and behavioural dimensions of stakeholder engagement.
 - iii. The third factor identified within this theme is **trust**, which was found to be a crucial building block in fostering engagement and collaboration among partners. Trust develops over time and fosters the collaboration by cultivating positive feelings among partners. The loss of trust, however, can negatively impact partners' expectations and feelings towards collaborating with your organisation, thereby impacting the emotional dimension of stakeholder engagement.
 - iv. The last factor identified within this theme to impact stakeholder engagement is the **presence of personal relationships between the partners of a collaboration**. Personal relationships were identified to be crucial to maintain engagement throughout a collaboration by stimulating the contact and communication between partners. Participants also noted that people tend to favour working with people they like, personal relationships can therefore also motivate participation. Face-to-face interactions were found to help in reaching this personal level of relationships between partners. Personal relationships can influence the cognitive dimension of stakeholder engagement, by supporting the future motivation to participate in projects with these partners.

4. Testing and validating the ERA Hubs framework through use cases

An important aspect of the COOPERATE ERA Hubs framework is its capacity to be applicable across different ecosystems, contexts and thematic areas. To do so, during the Phase 1 of the piloting actions, the COOPERATE project partners have developed four additional use cases (two in the Netherlands and two in Denmark) to test and fine tune the ERA Hubs framework and tools. In this section, we first present the insights coming from the Dutch use cases on the semiconductor and health ecosystems, before presenting the insights stemming from the Danish testing process and use cases.

4.1. Testing the model in the Netherlands: the semiconductors and health ecosystems as use cases

Two areas were selected to test the model: the semiconductors and health industry (see Box 3 and Box 4). These areas were chosen because they highlight areas where the Eindhoven ecosystem excels. In these fields, the four key players of the quadruple helix collaborate effectively to foster knowledge exchange, drive innovation, and promote growth (see Figure 11). The semiconductor industry has a strong presence in the region with a high number of patents within multiple companies. The health industry is of a different order with fewer patents spread over more companies. Therefore, it is interesting to see how both use cases are being represented and function in the Eindhoven ecosystem.

Figure 11: Patents Analysis Eindhoven 2000-2023

Source: Lens.org

Box 3: The semiconductor ecosystem in Eindhoven

The semiconductor ecosystem in Eindhoven is characterized by a dynamic interplay between academia, industry, government, and research institutions. The region, encompassing Eindhoven and its surroundings in the Netherlands, is part of one of Europe's most prominent semiconductor clusters, with a reputation for innovation and technological excellence²³.

- Eindhoven is home to **Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)**, renowned for its expertise in electrical engineering, materials science, and semiconductor technology. TU/e, alongside other research institutions like imec Netherlands, is a pivotal player in advancing semiconductor research, driving innovation from fundamental research to practical

²³ <https://www.pwc.nl/nl/actueel-publicaties/assets/pdfs/pwc-semicon-in-nl.pdf>

applications. This strong academic base fosters talent and generates cutting-edge research that fuels the semiconductor industry²⁴.

- The region hosts **major semiconductor companies** that play a significant role in the global market. Leading firms such as ASML²⁵ and NXP Semiconductors²⁶ have established their headquarters or major research and development centres in Eindhoven. These companies are instrumental in the development of advanced lithography machines, semiconductor components, and innovative technologies. The presence of these industry giants creates a robust environment for technological advancement and industrial growth.
- Eindhoven nurtures a **vibrant start-up ecosystem** in the semiconductor field. Numerous startups emerge from TU/e and other local institutions, focusing on various aspects of semiconductor technology, from materials and processes to new applications. Incubators and accelerators such as HighTechXL support these startups by providing mentoring, funding, and access to industry networks²⁷.
- The **Dutch government** actively supports the semiconductor sector through favourable policies, tax incentives, and substantial public investments. Programs and initiatives aimed at fostering innovation and maintaining the Netherlands' competitive edge in high-tech industries contribute to a thriving semiconductor ecosystem. The Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, along with regional bodies, play a crucial role in facilitating this support²⁸.

Box 4: Health industry

The health industry ecosystem in Eindhoven is characterized by a collaborative network of academia, industry, government, and healthcare institutions. Eindhoven is recognized for its innovation and strength in health technology, combining expertise in medical devices, digital health, and biotechnology²⁹.

- Eindhoven is anchored by **Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)**, which is internationally acclaimed for its research in biomedical engineering³⁰, health technology, and related fields. TU/e, alongside research institutions like the **Maxima Medical Center**³¹ is instrumental in driving forward research and innovation in the health sector. These institutions provide a strong foundation for both basic research and applied technologies, fostering advancements in medical devices, diagnostics, and therapeutic solutions. Eindhoven's health industry benefits from strong collaborations with local healthcare institutions. The Maxima Medical Center serve as a key partner in clinical research, testing new medical technologies, and implementing innovative health solutions. These collaborations facilitate the rapid translation of research into practical applications and enhance the adoption of new technologies in clinical settings.
- The health industry in Eindhoven is supported by **leading companies** that specialize in medical technology and health innovation. Major players include Philips Healthcare, which has a significant presence in Eindhoven and is renowned for its contributions to medical imaging, patient monitoring, and health informatics³².
- Eindhoven fosters a **dynamic start-up environment** in the health sector, with numerous start-ups emerging from TU/e and local incubators. These start-ups focus on various areas, including digital health solutions, medical devices, and biotechnologies. Incubators and accelerators such as HighTechXL and the Dutch health tech accelerator Holland Startup

24 <https://www.tue.nl/en/news-and-events/news-overview/18-04-2024-tue-strengthens-key-semicon-position-with-future-chips-flagship>

25 <https://www.asml.com/en>

26 <https://www.nxp.com/company/about-nxp/worldwide-locations/netherlands:NETHERLANDS>

27 <https://hightechxl.com/ecosystem/high-tech-campus-eindhoven-venture-builders-and-accelerators-competition-or-collaboration/>

28 <https://www.government.nl/latest/news/2024/03/28/the-netherlands-to-invest-%E2%82%AC2.5-billion-to-strengthen-business-climate-for-chip-industry-in-brainport-eindhoven>

29 <https://www.tue.nl/en/research/research-groups/eaisi/eaisi-business-operations/eindhoven-medtech-innovation-center>

30 <https://www.tue.nl/en/our-university/departments/biomedical-engineering>

31 <https://www.mmc.nl/english/maxima-medical-center>

32 <https://brainporteindhoven.com/int/for-you/business/sectors-technologies/medtech>

provide crucial support to these emerging companies, offering resources, mentorship, and access to a broad network of industry experts and investors³³.

- The **Dutch government** plays a proactive role in supporting the health industry through favourable policies, tax incentives, and significant public investments. Initiatives aimed at promoting health innovation and maintaining the Netherlands' competitive edge in medical technology are key to this support. The Ministry of Health, Welfare, and Sport, along with regional bodies such as Brainport Development, provides vital assistance to ensure a thriving health ecosystem³⁴.
- The connections between various stakeholders in the health industry are strengthened by **cluster organisations** such as the HealthTech Innovation Center (HTIC) and Brainport Development. HTIC promotes innovation and collaboration within the health tech sector by connecting industry players, researchers, and healthcare professionals. Brainport Development, on the other hand, supports the broader innovation ecosystem in the Brainport region, including health technology, by fostering partnerships and facilitating networking opportunities³⁵.

An interactive workshop session was organized involving key stakeholders with the aim of validating the model for assessing the maturity of an ERA Hub in both ecosystems. This session engaged a selected group of influential players from the ecosystems, representing all four elements of the quadruple helix, in a collaborative and dynamic discussion.

Table 5: List of attendees to the workshop

	Organisation	Function
1	Fontys University of Applied Science	Project leader, Lecturer/Researcher
2	University of Technology Eindhoven	Project Manager
3	VDL	Partnerships and ecosystem development
4	University of Technology Eindhoven	Program Coordinator
5	HighTechXL	Lead of partnerships
6	University of Technology Eindhoven	Doctoral researcher
7	Philips Healthcare	Program Manager
8	Orlando Vazquez Villegas	Doctoral researcher
9	University of Technology Eindhoven	Policy advisor
10	University of Technology Eindhoven	Policy advisor

After a brief introduction to the ERA Hub concept, the lines of action, and the use cases, participants were tasked with individually noting their knowledge about the semiconductor and health industry ecosystems. They then discussed their insights, identifying success factors and challenges in smaller groups. These findings were shared and reviewed with the larger group. The session concluded with a discussion on how the ERA Hub could provide support and address the identified challenges, enhancing the overall maturity of the ecosystem.

- **Insights from the semiconductor industry ecosystem**

During the workshop, several key factors were identified that supported the success of this industry in the region. One of the identified success factors was the **existence of a clear common goal**. Participants highlighted that working towards a circular economy was seen as a common goal, creating

33 <https://www.thisiseindhoven.com/en/work-and-study/7x-medtech-startups>

34 Dutch Global Health Strategy 2023-2030 Government of the Netherlands <https://www.government.nl › 2023/03/29 › Dutc...>

35 <https://brainporteindhoven.com/int/for-you/work/work-on/health>

a shared sense of urgency to collaborate. Additionally, attracting talent to the ecosystem was also seen as common goal of the industry. To support these goals, there is a clear roadmap to guide the industry's collaboration and innovation towards these common goals, which was also noted as a key success factor. IMEC was identified as a key player in this industry, facilitating knowledge creation and sharing throughout the industry.

However, the workshop also revealed **several challenges** existing in the industry. One important challenge that was identified was retaining and building upon the knowledge of previous collaborations and projects. Knowledge about specific projects or about the collaboration itself was often lost as it remained restricted to the partners of the project, resulting in a lot of 'reinventing-the-wheel' situations. One of the causes of this problem is the privacy issues regarding sharing the insights from certain projects. Another challenge relates to the common goal of the industry of attracting and building the necessary talent and competencies in the region. Participants suggested to address this problem by activating students through challenge-based learning in connection with current problems in the industry. Through this, knowledge creation and talent attraction can be supported. A last challenge identified was the involvement of civil society in collaborations. It was noted that how and when to include civil society in projects and collaborations remained difficult, particularly in comparison to the involvement of the other quadruple helices.

The workshop also explored potential roles for an ERA Hub in supporting this industry in the region. One of the roles identified was that ERA Hub policy could support the region in securing talent and funding. Additionally, it was suggested that an ERA Hub could facilitate outsourcing through interregional collaborations by connecting regions to support the specialization in these regions. If the regions in Europe are not sufficiently connected to support interregional collaboration there is a risk that talent moves to the developed regions, leading to talent drain in the lagging regions in Europe. An ERA Hub could therefore play a crucial role in mitigating this risk by strengthening the connections and collaborations between European regions.

- **Insights from the health industry ecosystem**

During the workshop key factors for the success of health industry in this region were also identified. The primary success factor identified by the participants was the existing trust between the organisations in the industry. It was noted that, in healthcare, it is difficult to innovate and develop products as you are dependent on the entire value chain. Breaking the individual silos of these players in the industry through a well-connected network is therefore crucial to facilitate innovation and collaboration. Trust was suggested to be the key component when developing such a well-connected network. Another important contributor to the success of the health industry in this region is the development and connection of health education and the industry. By closely connecting education and industry, the region supports continuous talent creation and retention, ensuring a steady inflow of professionals. Lastly, participants highlighted the importance of social awareness in the region in driving innovation. Social awareness in healthcare was found to drive the need for knowledge creation and valorisation, which enhances innovation in this industry.

However, also in this industry several challenges were identified in the workshop. For instance, scaling was suggested to be a big problem in healthcare application as the Dutch market alone is insufficient to support such scaling. Participants therefore emphasized the need to connect regions to allow start-ups and innovations to be scaled. It was also suggested that the ERA Hubs could support this by connecting the regions and assisting with policy requirements. Additionally, data collection and sharing was noted to remain a large challenge in this industry as healthcare data is often restricted to local boundaries. Overcoming these limitations is crucial for advancing innovation and collaboration across regions.

4.2. Testing the model in Denmark: the life science and sustainable technology ecosystems as use cases

In order to explore the Danish ecosystem, the players within it and the challenges they face, a series of activities were implemented.

An initial mapping aimed to identify the key stakeholders across the quadruple helix in the greater Copenhagen/Lyngby area (henceforth referred to as the Danish ecosystem).

To understand the ecosystem in greater depth, a survey was developed to further understanding the players, their role in the ecosystem, collaborations between ecosystem players and the challenges and opportunities they face in the ecosystem.

Building on this, two use cases were identified and tested with the maturity scores defined in the initial ERA Hubs framework (D1.1). The process is summarised in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Process for piloting the Danish ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project.

Identification of stakeholders

To gain a preliminary overview of the Danish ecosystem, an initial mapping of stakeholders was performed. This mapping focused on identifying key actors across the four aspects of the quadruple helix: academia, industry, public administration and the civil society. The mapping is summarised in Figure 13 and detailed below.

Figure 13: Outline of initial stakeholder mapping across the quadruple helix of the Danish ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project.

Academia

The Danish ecosystem boasts several universities delivering world-class education, research and innovation. The regional academic landscape is characterised by a high level of interdisciplinarity and collaboration, both between universities and between the academic world and the industry. In addition, the universities support innovation through academic innovation hubs. These hubs support startup formation and technology transfer to bridge the gap between scientific development and societal benefit.

Key actors include:

- Universities

- Technical University of Denmark
- University of Copenhagen
- Copenhagen Business School
- The IT University of Denmark
- Other Danish universities with a satellite presence in Copenhagen
- University hospitals, particularly Rigshospitalet.
- University innovation hubs
 - DTU Skylab
 - BioInnovation Institute
 - Copenhagen Science City
 - Copenhagen School of Entrepreneurship

Industry

The industrial landscape around Copenhagen and Lyngby is characterised by the presence of several global enterprises and a plethora of smaller companies. The region is home to a wide range of industrial fields, most notably life science/pharma, biotech, IT, logistics/shipping and sustainability/cleantech. The actors in the industrial landscape are supported by a vibrant startups culture and a diversity of soft funding and VC opportunities. Furthermore, the interests of the respective industrial fields are represented by a number of industry alliances and associations.

Key actors include:

- Multinational enterprises
 - A.P. Møller-Mærsk
 - Novo Nordisk
 - Novonesis
 - Ørsted
 - Carlsberg
 - Danfoss.
- Numerous SMEs and thriving startup landscape
- Public and private funding organisations
 - Innovation Fund Denmark
 - Novo Nordisk Foundation
 - The Danish Growth Fund
 - Venture capital firms (e.g. Sunstone, Eir Ventures, Nordic Alpha Partners, Seed Capital, PreSeed Ventures, etc)
- Private accelerators and incubators
 - DTU Science Park
 - Symbion
 - Accelerace
 - Copenhagen Bio Science Park (COBIS)
- Industry interest organisations
 - Medicon Valley Alliance
 - State of Green
 - Clean – Danish Water and Environmental Cluster
 - Copenhagen Capacity

Public administration

The government of Denmark is characterised by a strong and involved state with multiple layers of governance. Local, regional and national government entities work in concert within their respective areas of responsibility. The integration of municipalities, regional governments, and national agencies ensures a coordinated and efficient public administration.

Political goals emphasise research and innovation as drivers of growth, particularly within sustainability, health care, innovation, and infrastructure. Across political areas, the Danish government focuses on environmental sustainability, economic prosperity and social equality and justice.

Key actors include:

- Danish state, ministries and governmental agencies
 - Ministry of higher Education and Science
 - Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities, including the Danish Energy Agency
 - Ministry of the Interior and Health, including Danish Health Authority and Danish Medicines Agency
 - Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs, including the Danish Business Authority
 - Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark, including the Trade Council and Invest in Denmark
- The Capital Region of Denmark and the Zealand Region
- Municipalities, particularly Copenhagen Municipality and Lyngby-Taarbæk Municipality
- Regional innovation hubs
 - Erhvervshus Hovedstaden and Erhvervshus Sjælland (Business hubs of Capital Region and Zealand region, respectively)

Civil society

The involvement in the knowledge ecosystem around greater Copenhagen is as heterogeneous as the population. Patient organisations, NGOs, activist groups, and community organisations represent the interests of the civil society, contributing to public discourse, and influencing policies. The dissemination of scientific progress to the wider public also largely happens through these organisations, but also through the media and public discourse on topics of wider interest. In addition, direct dissemination initiatives allow scientists to present their findings directly to interested citizens through popular dissemination activities.

Key actors include:

- Patient organisations
 - Danish Cancer Society
 - The Heart Association
 - Asthma-Allergy Denmark
- NGOs
 - Danish Society for Public Health
 - Danish Society for Nature Conservation
 - Green Transition Denmark
- Civil activist organisations
 - NOAH – Friends of the Earth Denmark
 - Local environmental initiatives, e.g. community gardens, recycling programmes, green living workshops
- National and independent media and public discourse
- Popular science disseminators, e.g. Science and Cocktails

Detailed mapping of ecosystem

In order to identify the challenges and opportunities faced by ecosystem members, a survey was distributed. The survey was drafted by IDEA based on information from DTU with a specific focus on the objectives and needs of the ecosystem. The survey includes a condensed introduction and context of the COOPERATE project to ensure that stakeholders are sufficiently informed about the project prior to engaging in the survey.

The survey consists of 31 questions, focusing on the motivations, benefits and challenges relevant to the Danish ecosystem stakeholders. The questions examine the general role of stakeholder organisations within the quadruple helix framework and assesses collaboration activities at different levels – national, regional, and local – providing insights into the extent of collaborative efforts. To gain a broader perspective beyond the primary region, the survey includes inquiries about interregional collaboration and the associated benefits within ecosystems.

The survey delves into the seven lines of action (research, talent, knowledge transfer, funding, collaboration, governance, and innovation) as critical elements that shape stakeholders’ overarching goals. Furthermore, stakeholders are asked to identify their primary collaboration partners within the quadruple helix. This allows for a detailed analysis, enabling stakeholders to elaborate on specific collaboration arrangements.

Understanding stakeholders’ motivations for active participation in the ecosystem is pivotal. The survey poses targeted questions, such as: “What drives your organisation’s engagement in the ecosystem?” Response options include branding, knowledge sharing, partnerships, talent recruitment, specific focus areas (e.g., AI, pharma, tech, HR, ESG), and other factors. Moreover, the survey investigates perceived benefits of participating in the Danish ecosystem. Stakeholders participating in the survey can articulate concrete advantages they associate with ecosystem involvement.

A dedicated section of the survey focuses on stakeholders’ collaboration with DTU. It explores the motivations behind engaging with DTU and maps this collaboration to specific activities along the lines of action (research, talent development, knowledge transfer, funding, collaboration, governance, and innovation). Stakeholders are also invited to share their perceived benefits from participating in DTU’s activities and programs.

Finally, the survey addresses challenges faced by stakeholders in collaborating with other actors, particularly concerning the development of new innovations and knowledge building.

The survey concludes with questions focusing on the stakeholder’s desire to participate in follow-up workshops and roundtable discussion related to the COOPERATE project.

Stakeholders consulted

The survey was distributed to 33 players across the ecosystem, representing all four aspects of the quadruple helix. It was answered by 11 individuals where 1 person is categorised as being from Research, 3 people are from the Public/ government or agency, 3 people are from the category Business and 4 people are from civil society. The respondents are summarised in Table 6.

Table 6: Survey respondents to mapping of Danish ecosystem

No.	Organisation	Category
1	EIR Ventures	Business
2	Alfa Laval Copenhagen	Business
3	We Build Denmark/DOLL Living Lab	Civil Society
4	Lyngby Handelsskole U/NORD	Civil Society
5	The Municipality of Lyngby-Taarbæk	Public administration
6	Uhrbrand	Civil Society
7	Ørestad Innovation City Copenhagen (OICC)	Public administration
8	Erhvervshus Hovedstaden	Public administration
9	Technical University of Denmark	Research
10	Polyteknisk Kollegieselskab	Civil Society
11	Vermilion Racing	Business

Results of analysis

The results of the survey showed that Collaboration was the most important element for the overarching goal of the organisation while Talent and Innovation came in on a shared second place (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Responses from survey

9. Which of the following elements are important for your organisations overarching goal?

[More Details](#)

Source: COOPERATE project.

When asked about the main type of organisation the stakeholders collaborate with, the highest scoring organisation was Business followed by Public/government or agency. Partnerships were identified as the main motivation for the stakeholder's organisation to engage in the ecosystem. Knowledge sharing was also identified as a key motivation for engaging in the ecosystem (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Responses from survey

13. What is the basis for the motivation of your organisation to engage in the ecosystem?

[More Details](#)

Source: COOPERATE project.

When the stakeholders were asked about the perceived benefits of their organization for participating in the Danish ecosystem the following responses were documented.

- “We seek our exceptional high value opportunities based on Nordic innovation. Denmark has a strong tradition in life science innovation.”
- “Insights into new technologies, markets, business opportunities, being part of something bigger than we can manage on our own.”
- “Meeting people with similar challenges and solutions.”
- “Supporting the goals of our innovation district.”

The above statements support the notion that the motivation for participation in the ecosystem is indeed to share knowledge and develop partnerships. The perceived benefits for the stakeholder’s organisation for participating in the Danish ecosystem is illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Word cloud describing respondents' main motivation for operating in the Danish ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project.

The survey also focuses on the extent to which an ERA Hub concept would be beneficial and/or complementary to the stakeholders and their organisation. There was a diversity in the answers for this section:

- “It is difficult for me to point to any advantages of an ERA Hub. For me the concept seems like a rather duplication of existing initiative, and I struggle to see the “need-to-have” elements of this, i.e. what needs that are not addressed today will an ERA Hub address? I would rather like to see some consolidation of existing initiatives.”
- “I think it makes sense to have a Hub for collaboration, to show that it’s possible to make more value together than one by one.”
- “Very: Access to student developers, co-hosting sprints, sparring etc. Help to get startups closer to the market.”
- “Could be very beneficial as our innovation district is characterised by all the ERA Hub elements.”

Regarding collaboration, more than 80% of the stakeholders answered that their organisation collaborates with other organisations outside of their region. The benefits of participating in interregional collaboration among ecosystems was also a focus area of the survey. To this end, the stakeholders answered that the following were key to participate in interregional collaboration- transfer of knowledge, international endeavour, experience exchange, EU regulation, global scale, new views and across countries.

On the other hand, when the stakeholders were asked about the main challenges that their organisation face in collaboration with other actors regarding the development of new innovation and knowledge building, they answered as follows;

- “The overarching problem in the Nordics is that lack of professional capital. Generalist investors (pension funds, endowments, banks etc..) do not invest in the sector, and financial constraints are severe.”
- “Time and acceptance to use the time for collaboration if no direct output is identified.”

- “...actors are hesitant to share their data.”

The overall result of the survey shows that the primary goal for the stakeholders' organisations to participate in the Danish ecosystem is focused on innovation, talent and collaboration. The primary motivation for participation in the Danish ecosystem is focused on partnerships and knowledge sharing, while the benefits are insights, new opportunities, like-minded people, and funding. Some of the challenges the stakeholders mention when participating in the Danish ecosystem is time, partner match, regulation, culture and capital.

Identified use cases

The two use cases, life science and sustainable technology, were selected from amongst the areas in which the Danish ecosystem possesses particular expertise and where the four players of the quadruple helix work in concert to drive knowledge exchange, innovation, and growth.

Life science

The Danish life science ecosystem is characterised by a well-developed interplay between academia, industry, government, and healthcare institutions. The region, also including southern Sweden, is collectively referred to as the Medicon Valley and makes up one of Europe's strongest life science clusters³⁶.

The Danish universities and research institutions are internationally recognised for their excellence in biomedical research, biotechnology, and pharmaceutical science³⁷. This hotbed of talent and world-class medical research drives the development of innovative solutions in the ecosystem all the way from student innovation through to industrial R&D in multinational companies like Novo Nordisk, Lundbeck, Genmab and Novonosis, who are industry leaders in diabetes, neuroscience, oncology and industrial enzymes, respectively. These major corporations have been retained within the Danish borders by attractive conditions for doing business in Denmark, including favourable policies and a competitive tax rate, well-functioning infrastructure, availability of talent and heavy public investment into the life science sector: diabetes, neuroscience, oncology and industrial enzymes, respectively. These major corporations have been retained within the Danish borders by attractive conditions for doing business in Denmark, including favourable policies and a competitive tax rate, well-functioning infrastructure, availability of talent and heavy public investment into the life science sector.

In addition to the major established companies, the Danish life science ecosystem supports a vibrant start-up culture, with many biotech and medtech startups emerging from universities such as the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and the University of Copenhagen, to be nurtured in incubators and accelerators. One noteworthy example of the latter includes the BioInnovation Institute, founded in 2019 by the Novo Nordisk Foundation in order to bridge the gap between ground-breaking scientific research and its commercialisation in the life science sector³⁸.

Denmark's public healthcare system collaborates readily with the life science industry, providing a platform for testing solutions and running clinical research, in turn leading to rapid translation of medical research into practice and facilitates the adoption of new medical technologies. This is further supported by a streamlined regulatory environment, promoted by agencies like the Danish Medicines Agency and the Danish Health Authority that facilitates clinical trials and the commercialization of new therapies.

The connections between the players in the life science ecosystem are supported by the Medicon Valley Alliance, a non-profit cluster organisation aiming to facilitate networking and collaboration across the ecosystem³⁹.

³⁶ <https://mediconvalley.greatercphregion.com/about-medicon-valley>

³⁷ <https://investindk.com/set-up-a-business/life-sciences>

³⁸ <https://bii.dk/about/>

³⁹ <https://mva.org/about-mva/vision-mission/>

Sustainable technology

The ecosystem around sustainable solutions in Denmark is growing, driving innovation in renewable energy, green technology, and sustainable urban development. This development is closely aligned with both national environmental goals and societal values.

DTU is one of the region's key academic players in advancing sustainable technologies. Indeed, sustainability takes centre stage as one of the three pillars of DTU's strategy⁴⁰. The university encourages interdisciplinarity between research fields to develop a broad palette of sustainable solutions, and also supports a vibrant and passionate start-up community within sustainability. Once these start-ups graduate from the university setting, they are often further supported by public and private incubators and accelerators in the neighbourhood, such as DTU Science Park, who is Denmark's biggest deep-tech community⁴¹ or Accelerace, which provide funding, mentoring, and access to networks⁴².

One of the most internationally well-known faces of the Danish sustainability agenda is the country's dedication to renewable energy, particularly wind power. Companies like Ørsted and Vestas operate at the forefront of wind energy innovation, providing cutting-edge technology and expertise worldwide. The industry is supported by ambitious energy policies, aiming for Denmark to be fossil fuel-free by 2050⁴³. The Danish government supports this transition with policies that incentivize green innovation, such as tax exemptions for renewable energy projects and stringent energy efficiency standards (Renewable energy policy database and support: Denmark⁴⁴).

Furthermore, the Danish ecosystem surrounding sustainable solutions focuses on sustainable urban planning and smart city solutions, with Copenhagen aiming to be carbon neutral by 2025. Copenhagen is famous for its cycling culture and infrastructure, and there is a great political focus on sustainability in the rapid expansion of the building mass and heating systems of the capital. Oil, gas and private fireplaces are being phased out in favour of district heating, which in turn is transitioning towards more sustainable sources⁴⁵. In addition, the demand for central cooling is growing in Denmark. As of 2023, one third of Copenhagen's hotel rooms were cooled with seawater, delivered by the capital's utility service, Høfor, saving up to 70% CO₂ emissions compared to conventional electric air conditioning⁴⁶.

Other areas like energy-efficient pumps, cooling systems, and sustainable building materials are pioneered by companies like Grundfos, Danfoss, and Rockwool. Denmark's commitment to sustainability is also reflected in its active participation in international climate agreements and its role as a pioneer in implementing sustainable development goals (SDGs)⁴⁷.

Danish companies and research institutions frequently collaborate with international partners to develop and deploy sustainable technologies, making Denmark a hub for global green innovation. One of the central access points to the green solutions stage in Denmark is the network State of Green, who works to connect Danish and international partners to facilitate knowledge sharing and accelerate the transition towards a sustainable future⁴⁸.

A remarkable feature of the sustainable solutions use case is the very visible presence of the often-overlooked fourth player of the quadruple helix: the civil society. There is a strong public involvement in

40 <https://issuu.com/dtudk/docs/dtu-strategi-2020-2025-uk>

41 <https://dtusciencespark.com/>

42 <https://accelerace.io/>

43 <https://ens.dk/en/our-responsibilities/energy-climate-politics/danish-climate-policies>.

44 <http://www.res-legal.eu/search-by-country/denmark/>

45 <https://www.kefm.dk/aktuelt/nyheder/2024/apr/ny-rapport-viser-fremgang-i-udrulning-af-groen-varme->

46 <https://stateofgreen.com/en/news/one-third-of-copenhagens-hotel-rooms-are-now-cooled-with-seawater/>

47 <https://um.dk/en/danida/strategies-and-priorities/the-un-sustainable-development-goals>

48 <https://stateofgreen.com/en/>

the transition to a more sustainable future, with civil activism and public discourse revolving around themes like circular economy, recycling waste materials, and reducing meat consumption.

Testing the maturity assessment

Workshop design

A roundtable was called in order to involve the ecosystem stakeholders in validating the model for assessing the maturity of an ERA Hub. For this roundtable, a gender-balanced selection of impactful players in the ecosystem was invited, representing all four elements of the quadruple helix. Table 7 lists the participants in the workshop.

Table 7: Workshop participants

	Organisation	Function
1	Ørestad Innovation City Copenhagen	Development Consultant
2	Copenhagen Capacity	Talent Attraction
3	Novo Nordisk Foundation	Finance Business Partner
4	Clair Scientific and DTU	CEO/Co-founder and Associate Professor
5	Paint'R	CEO/Co-founder

Source: COOPERATE project.

The workshop was designed as a qualitative evaluation of the use cases, applying the COOPERATE maturity scores to the seven lines of action.

Figure 17 depicts the five levels of maturity defined in the Initial ERA Hubs framework (D1.1). At the lowest level, Absence, there are little or no interaction between ecosystem players, few resources and only scattered, isolated initiatives. At the next level, Emergence, we see beginning communication and information exchange between ecosystem players. At the Development level, there is coordinated networking and a certain degree of intent behind the interactions. At the Diffusion level, there is loose coordination towards the achievement of compatible goals and at the highest level, Collaboration, there are joint activities and co-creation based on a joint strategy. This Collaboration level is where the four actors of the quadruple helix truly come together to lift the ecosystem and drive progress.

Figure 17: Maturity evaluation scale as defined in the initial ERA Hubs framework (D1.1)

Source: COOPERATE project, adapted from *Leveraging complexity for ecosystem innovation* Russel and Smorodinskaya (2018).

Table 8 lists the seven lines of action as well as the hallmarks of a well-functioning knowledge ecosystem within each line of action, as described in more detail in the COOPERATE Playbook (D2.1).

Table 8: Hallmarks of well-functioning ecosystems within each line of action as defined by the COOPERATE Playbook, release 1 (D2.1)

Line of action	Hallmarks
Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High citation index and publication output • High number of scientific employees • Presence of large research centres • Diversity of research areas • Availability of research and development investment
Talent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low unemployment for scientific professionals • Ability to attract talent from outside the ecosystem • Liveability of local area and presence of attractive workplaces
Knowledge transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of trust between ecosystem players • Stable knowledge exchange framework • Engaging formats of knowledge transfer
Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity and availability of funding • Transparent grant practices • Constructive feedback on proposals
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal collaboration agreements • Long-term strategic partnerships • Tangible outcomes • High level of trust and openness
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust and transparency • Long-term political support • Public discourse and open discussion • Clear definition of roles and responsibilities • Frequent review of strategy and impact with control mechanisms
Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High number of patents filed and granted • Presence of licensing agreements • High number of start-ups • Availability of innovation talent, mentorship and education

Source: COOPERATE project.

In the workshop, the participants were given a brief introduction to the ERA Hub concept, the lines of action, the maturity scoring system, and the use cases. After this initial information, participants were divided into two groups. Each group was assigned one use case to discuss, collectively reaching a score for each of the seven lines of action, which were then discussed in the larger group. Finally, a short time was set aside for discussing the utility of the ERA Hubs maturity scores on a general level and whether the scoring system is sufficient and adequate to describe the maturity of an ERA Hub.

Scoring of use cases

Table 9 below shows the scores and reflections on the life science use case and Table 10 shows the scores and reflections on the sustainable technology case.

Table 9: Scores and reflections for Life science use case

Line of action	Score	Reflections
Research	4	<p>Copenhagen performs very strongly within research according to international rankings, boasting centres of excellence within stem cells, neurology and cardiovascular disease. The output volume in absolute numbers is low - a natural consequence of being a small country - but the quality is world-class. However, Denmark is "brilliantly silent": excellent but quiet about it. Consequentially, the quality of Danish research is not fully internationally recognised.</p> <p>There is a great diversity of research areas and some joint research efforts, but the ecosystem lacks overall coordination and joint goals.</p> <p>To reach the highest level of integration across the quadruple helix, the civil society needs to be more engaged in order to break down the "ivory tower".</p>
Talent	3	<p>Talent attraction is the no. 1 challenge in every business. The Danish educational system is first class, and the talent mass is highly skilled but not sufficient in volume to meet the demand from the industry.</p> <p>To complement home-grown talent, international talent attraction is paramount. However, the very top researchers do not come to Denmark because they don't know Denmark, the quality of Danish research, or the societal attractions of living in Denmark.</p> <p>The approach to talent attraction is not fully coordinated. Denmark requires a national strategy for attracting and retaining international talent.</p>
Knowledge transfer	5	<p>The Danish society is renowned for a high level of trust between ecosystem players. Over the past ten years, there has been a development in the Tech Transfer Offices of the Danish universities, moving towards more open collaboration rather than locking every conversation under NDAs.</p> <p>Furthermore, most development projects that achieve funding has knowledge sharing at the core of their mission. A prime example is quantum research that sees an exceptional level of coordination between the actors in the ecosystem.</p>
Funding	3	<p>Within the life science area, the grant processes are transparent and there is plenty of pre-seed and seed funding available for startups. However, when the time comes to scale up the businesses, it is necessary for scaleups to look abroad for funding.</p> <p>There is a lack of a venture culture/environment, and we haven't seen a life science IPO in many years.</p>
Collaboration	3	<p>Denmark is characterised by a high level of trust and openness, and partners are very willing to enter dialogues. However, while partners readily share knowledge, it rarely leads to actual collaboration and there are few tangible outcomes.</p> <p>One example is the attraction of international talent. This needs to happen in collaboration between academia and the industry to ensure that the international graduates are able to find a satisfying job in Denmark after completing their education.</p>
Governance	2	<p>There are perhaps too many actors on the Danish stage, as illustrated by the annual mapping of the Danish innovation ecosystem counting some 200 actors. It is not always clear how they complement each other and how they</p>

		<p>all contribute to a common goal. A regular “house cleaning” to eliminate some initiatives and combine others might make the ecosystem offerings more efficient. However, the ecosystem lacks a central player that has the overview and owns the joint agenda.</p> <p>Politically speaking, the long-term strategy is not always clear on a national level (as opposed to EU-level). Political support for life science research and development goes up and down and there is a need for more stable political and public support and investment in order to cement life science as a Danish powerhouse. This includes prioritising fundamental research as well as applied research.</p>
Innovation	4	<p>Innovation is highly prioritised both politically, academically and in the industry, and it is attractive to work with innovation and entrepreneurship as a student. There is a good collaboration between the startup houses in Denmark and the administrative barriers to starting a business are low - it takes 10 minutes to start a company in Denmark. Taken together, this ensures a high output of startups - the survival rate of these startups may be a different story.</p> <p>However, the collaboration between universities around student-driven innovation is insufficient. Each university has their own startup support organisation, which is maybe not the most efficient setup. Sweden has the Stockholm School of Entrepreneurship - why can't we do something similar in Denmark? In a small country like Denmark, it should be possible to have one joint powerhouse with different verticals rather than several smaller initiatives.</p>

Source: COOPERATE project.

Table 10: Scores and reflections for Sustainable technology use case

Line of action	Score	Reflections
Research	5	The research ecosystem around Copenhagen and Lyngby is "top shot" across the various aspects of sustainable technology.
Talent	3.5	Denmark is an attractive place to live and work once you get to know it, but it is a small place and struggles to compete with major hubs like Oxford or the Bay Area. The very top of international talent will not come to Denmark. Denmark also is not a frontrunner on the business side.
Knowledge transfer	2	<p>The tech transfer offices work under restrictive boundaries and have a reputation for being difficult to work with but do a good job within the restrictions they work under.</p> <p>DTU prioritises having scientific employees participate in public dissemination activities as part of their job to bridge the gap between academia and the remaining ecosystem players.</p> <p>Many players start initiatives, but participants remark it is easier to get funding than functional collaboration as many larger companies are very closed off. There is a high level of trust within the Danish ecosystem, but no stable knowledge exchange frameworks, and it is difficult to know which doors to knock on.</p>
Funding	5	Sustainability is a hot topic and there are many funding programmes dedicated to sustainability. There is a lot of soft funding available for startups, but not so much hard funding. When you need funding to scale, you often need to look abroad.

Collaboration	2	It has been difficult to establish collaborations in the ecosystem and everybody wants something, and many actors want to charge to act as middlemen. It is difficult for startups to set up collaborations with companies to test technologies unless they offer something that exceeds state of the art. However, the larger companies are generally willing to buy once the product is finished.
Governance	2	There is currently a lot of political discourse and awareness around sustainability. Some three-party agreements are being developed, but e.g. startups are not included. There needs to be an open discussion involving startups and academia as well as the established industry. There is no focal point of coordination in the ecosystem.
Innovation	5	Innovation is high on the political agenda, and this is backed up by the universities. DTU in particular is producing a lot of startups, and the innovation agenda has support across the academic landscape, especially championed by the president of DTU.

Source: COOPERATE project.

Discussion of results

The evaluation of the two use cases is summarised in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Results from ecosystem maturity scoring session

Source: COOPERATE project.

The two groups agreed that the Copenhagen/Lyngby ecosystem performs strongly within research and innovation but leaves room for improvement within talent attraction and retention and particularly within governance and collaboration. There is greater disagreement between the two use cases when it comes to the evaluation of knowledge transfer and funding. However, it is not unexpected that there is a discrepancy between the two as they are two distinct ecosystems/ERA Hubs within the same geographical region.

Considering that this is the region that tops the EU Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS), the scores are perhaps lower than one might expect. This only underlines that the hallmarks in the Playbook describe an ideal and that an ecosystem is neither required nor expected to excel in every aspect to be an ERA Hub. Indeed, even strong ecosystems can improve.

It is worth noting that these results are based on a qualitative discussion. One element that may have affected the scores is that the Danish ecosystem in general has a great focus on improvement and identifying development potential. Thus, the participants may have been overly critical of the ecosystem in which they operate. Indeed, this attitude is most likely a central reason why the region in its entirety performs well on the RIS.

Across the two use cases, some common issues were identified. Both groups of stakeholders commented that the absence of a central coordinating unit led to fragmented offerings and hindered the joint agenda. Furthermore, while the Danish ecosystem enjoys a high level of trust between members of the ecosystem, this leads only to knowledge sharing and not actual collaboration. In terms of talent, both groups noted that while Denmark is an attractive place to live and work, it is not big enough to compete with the major global hubs (Oxford, Bay Area) for the very top talent. Finally, there was agreement on the fact that while pre-seed and seed funding is plentiful, funding for scaling is largely unavailable in Denmark and needs to be sourced abroad.

Discussion of utility of model

Participants were generally positive, seeing the maturity scores as an interesting tool to evaluate the maturity of an ecosystem, whether national, regional or more local. The use cases are aligned with the two main focus areas of Copenhagen Capacity who sees this tool as an interesting lens to evaluate their efforts to promote these two strongholds of regional progress.

Participants were not fully convinced whether the university is the natural focal point of an ERA Hub constellation, as elements like governance and shaping the funding landscape are typically not driven by universities.

5. Conclusion

The information gathered in this report serve to sustain the development of the ERA Hubs framework on several dimensions. First, by testing the model in different ecosystems across Europe and with a different thematic focus helps the COOPERATE project team to improve and refine the model and the associated tools, most notably the Playbook, the Toolbox and the Self-assessment (and the associated KPIs). In addition, the piloting of the activities in Czechia together with the additional four use cases from the Netherlands and Denmark help us to analyse the applicability of the model from different perspectives:

- the Czech pilot use case contributes to a better understanding of the needs of an emerging ecosystem and how the ERA Hubs framework and tools can contribute to its future development (i.e. AI in the Prague region),
- the Dutch case study analyses the needs and challenges related to ecosystem stakeholder engagement in interregional collaboration settings,
- The Dutch use cases on the semiconductor and health ecosystems shed light on the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework in the light of the needs and characteristics of these ecosystems.
- The Danish use cases on life sciences and sustainable technologies contribute to a better understanding of the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework and provides a good basis to improve the tools to measure the maturity of ecosystems (KPIs).

These elements contribute to ensure the future applicability of the model in different settings. The insights gained through the Danish, Dutch and Czech case studies and use cases were presented in the COOPERATE Co-creation session that took place on the 23rd of September 2024. This Co-creation session also served to bring together the insights from the piloting activities and to identify common denominators and challenges when applying the ERA Hubs framework and tools. The information gathered in this session will be considered in the next steps of the project, particularly in the revision of the Playbook and the Toolbox in view of their use in Phase 2 piloting activities. In addition, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be used for measuring the maturity of the ecosystems through the self-assessment tool were also presented and discussed in the abovementioned Co-creation session. The combination of use cases and concrete indicators to measure maturity led to important suggestions from participants to improve the measurement tools. These suggestions will be considered in the further refinement of the KPIs for the self-assessment tool.

6. Bibliography

Accelerace. <https://accelerace.io/>

AI Summit Prague. (2023). Event Overview and Insights. Retrieved from AI Summit Website.

ASML. <https://www.asml.com/en>

BioInnovation Institute, About BII. <https://bii.dk/about/>

Bioinnovation Institute. <https://bii.dk/about/>

Brainport Eindhoven. <https://brainporteindhoven.com/int/for-you/business/sectors-technologies/medtech>

Brainport Eindhoven. <https://brainporteindhoven.com/int/for-you/work/work-on/health>

CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/projects>

ČVUT. (2023). AI Research and Innovation. Retrieved from ČVUT Website.

ČVUT. (2023). AI Research and Innovation. Retrieved from ČVUT Website.

Czech National Innovation Fund. (2023). Collaboration Analysis Report. Retrieved from Government Portal.

Czech Startups. (2023). Leading AI Startups in the Czech Republic. Retrieved from Startup Directory.

CzechInvest. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in the Czech Republic: Opportunities and Challenges. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

CzechInvest. (2022). Czech National Innovation Fund Report. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

CzechInvest. (2022). Investment Landscape for AI Startups in Czechia. Retrieved from CzechInvest Website.

Danish Energy Agency. Danish climate policies. <https://ens.dk/en/our-responsibilities/energy-climate-politics/danish-climate-policies>

Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities. Ny rapport viser fremgang i udrulning af grøn varme (article only available in Danish). <https://www.kefm.dk/aktuelt/nyheder/2024/apr/ny-rapport-viser-fremgang-i-udrulning-af-groen-varme->

Deloitte. (2023). Workforce Challenges in the AI Sector. Retrieved from Deloitte Insights.

DTU (2020). DTU Strategi 2020-2025. <https://issuu.com/dtudk/docs/dtu-strategi-2020-2025-uk>

DTU Science Park. <https://dtusciencepark.com/>

Eindhoven Medtech Innovation Centre. <https://www.tue.nl/en/research/research-groups/eaisi/eaisi-business-operations/eindhoven-medtech-innovation-center>

European Innovation Scoreboard 2024. <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

European Research Area Policy Agenda 2022-2024. <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

Government of the Netherlands (2023). Dutch Global Health Strategy 2023-2030 <https://www.government.nl/documents/publications/2023/03/29/dutch-global-health-strategy>

Government of the Netherlands (2024). <https://www.government.nl/latest/news/2024/03/28/the-netherlands-to-invest-%E2%82%AC2.5-billion-to-strengthen-business-climate-for-chip-industry-in-brainport-eindhoven>

Hightechxl. <https://hightechxl.com/ecosystem/high-tech-campus-eindhoven-venture-builders-and-accelerators-competition-or-collaboration/>

Hlavačka, J., & Novotný, P. (2021). AI Applications in the Czech Industry. Journal of Technology and Information. Retrieved from Journal Website

Invest in Denmark. <https://investindk.com/set-up-a-business/life-sciences>

Invest in Denmark. The leading life science cluster in Europe. <https://investindk.com/set-up-a-business/life-sciences>

Jonas, J. M., Boha, J., Sörhammar, D., & Moeslein, K. M. (2018). Stakeholder engagement in intra- and inter-organizational innovation: Exploring antecedents of engagement in service ecosystems. Journal of Service Management, 29(3), 399–421. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOSM-09-2016-0239>

Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A., & Laude, D. (2022). Stakeholder Engagement: Past, Present, and Future. Business and Society, 61(5), 1136–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211066595>

Maxima Medical Centre. <https://www.mmc.nl/english/maxima-medical-center>

Medicon Valley Alliance. <https://mva.org/about-mva/vision-mission/>

Medicon Valley. <https://mediconvalley.greatercphregion.com/about-medicon-valley>

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark. The UN Sustainable development goals. <https://um.dk/en/danida/strategies-and-priorities/the-un-sustainable-development-goals>

Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. (2023). National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence. Retrieved from Government Portal.

National Artificial Intelligence Strategy of the Czech Republic. Online. 2019. https://www.mpo.gov.cz/assets/en/guidepost/for-the-media/press-releases/2019/5/NAIS_eng_web.pdf

National Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation of the Czech Republic 2021-2027. Online. 2021. https://www.ris3.cz/sites/default/files/National-RIS3-Strategy_2.pdf

NXP. <https://www.nxp.com/company/about-nxp/worldwide-locations/netherlands:NETHERLANDS>

Přehled inovační infrastruktury. <https://www.ris3.cz/monitoring/regionalni-dimenze-ris3/inovacni-ekosystemy-v-krajich/mapovani-inovacnich-ekosystemu-czechinvest/mapovani-inovacnich-infrastruktur-v-cesku>

Přehled inovační infrastruktury. Online. <https://www.ris3.cz/monitoring/regionalni-dimenze-ris3/inovacni-ekosystemy-v-krajich/mapovani-inovacnich-ekosystemu-czechinvest/mapovani-inovacnich-infrastruktur-v-cesku>

PWC (2024). Semicon in NL. <https://www.pwc.nl/nl/actueel-publicaties/assets/pdfs/pwc-semicon-in-nl.pdf>

RES LEGAL. Denmark: Overall summary. <http://www.res-legal.eu/search-by-country/denmark/>

State of Green. One third of Copenhagen's hotel rooms are now cooled with seawater. <https://stateofgreen.com/en/news/one-third-of-copenhagens-hotel-rooms-are-now-cooled-with-seawater/>

State of Green. State of Green. <https://stateofgreen.com/en/>

Technical University of Denmark. Strategy 2020-2025 – Technology for People. <https://issuu.com/dtudk/docs/dtu-strategi-2020-2025-uk>

This is Eindhoven. <https://www.thisiseindhoven.com/en/work-and-study/7x-medtech-startups>

TU/e (2024). <https://www.tue.nl/en/news-and-events/news-overview/18-04-2024-tue-strengthens-key-semicon-position-with-future-chips-flagship>

TU/e . <https://www.tue.nl/en/our-university/departments/biomedical-engineering>

Widén, K., Olander, S., & Atkin, B. (2014). Links between Successful Innovation Diffusion and Stakeholder Engagement. Journal of Management in Engineering, 30(5). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)me.1943-5479.0000214](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)me.1943-5479.0000214)